

SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW OF EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS ON THE SOCIAL ACCEPTABILITY OF CaL-BASED CCUS TECHNOLOGIES

Deliverable D6.3

D6.3 Systematic literature review of empirical analyses on the social acceptability of CaL-based CCUS technologies

Deliverable title	D6.3 Systematic literature review of empirical analyses on the social acceptability of CaL-based CCUS technologies
Work Package	WP6
Lead beneficiary	CSIC
Due Date	31/7/2023
Actual delivery date	19/7/2023
Dissemination level	Public
Abstract	D6.3 provides a systematic review of the literature on the level of knowledge/awareness of CCUS technologies, their social acceptability and the drivers and barriers of such social acceptability.
Project Acronym	CaLby2030
Project Call	HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-02-13
Type of Action	HORIZON EUROPE - Research and Innovation Action
Project Start Date	01/10/2022
Project duration	42 months
Grant Number	101075416

Disclaimer

The statements in this report are the outcome of a systematic review process carried out by the authors and do not reflect the views of the European Commission. The usual disclaimer applies.

VERSION	DATE	MODIFICATION	PREPARED BY (Main contributors)	APPROVED BY
1	June 5th 2023	Initial version	IPP-CSIC and ICMAN-CSIC Pablo del Río Jose L. Oviedo	IPP-CSIC and ICMAN-CSIC
2	June 23rd 2023	Second version	IPP-CSIC and ICMAN-CSIC Pablo del Río Jose L. Oviedo	IPP-CSIC, ICMAN-CSIC and review team
3	July 10th	Third version	IPP-CSIC and ICMAN-CSIC Pablo del Río Jose L. Oviedo	WP6 partners
4	July 18th	Fourth version	IPP-CSIC and ICMAN-CSIC Pablo del Río Jose L. Oviedo	Executive Board, Project Management Team and rest of the consortium

Table of contents

1	INTRODUCTION	7
2	METHODOLOGY	7
2.1	WHAT IS A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW?	7
2.2	Why a systematic review?	8
2.3	How was our systematic review carried out?	9
3	RESULTS OF THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW	13
3.1	Final selection of articles.	13
3.2	Journals	17
3.3	Surveys over the years	17
3.4	Geographical distribution	18
3.5	Stage analysed	18
3.6	Acceptability focus settings	19
3.7	Source of survey data	19
3.8	Sample size	20
3.9	Method type	20
4	MAIN FINDINGS	21
4.1	CCUS knowledge/awareness	21
4.2	CCUS acceptance	25
4.3	Drivers and barriers of CCUS acceptance.	33
4.3.1	Broad and specific categories.	33
4.3.2	Drivers/enablers.	33
4.3.2.1	Drivers per broad category and item	34
4.3.2.2	Summary of drivers	39
4.3.3	Barriers	39
4.3.3.1	Barriers per broad category and item.	39
4.3.3.2	Summary of barriers	44
4.3.4	Not relevant items.	45
4.3.5	Synthesis.	46
5	CONCLUSIONS	47

1 INTRODUCTION

Social acceptability is arguably one of the main barriers to the development and deployment of carbon capture, utilisation and storage (CCUS) technologies (IPCC 2022, IRENA 2022, Tcvetkov et al 2019). Accordingly, subtask 6.2.1. of the CaLby2030 project is devoted to this topic. The aim of this deliverable is to meet the requirement of Subtask 6.2.1 of the Grant Agreement of the CaLby2030 project (page 18 of DoA), according to which:

Subtask 6.2.1 Systematic literature review (M1-M10). A “systematic literature review” on the topic will be performed, looking for previous empirical analyses on the social acceptability of CCUS technologies. This methodology, widely accepted for social science investigations, will provide relevant insights on the drivers and barriers to the social acceptability of CCUS projects. D6.3 will report the results of this systematic literature review, which will feed into the design of the survey in subtask 6.2.2

The systematic review performed in this task stands by itself, but it can also be deemed instrumental for Subtask 6.2.2 “Survey design for assessing the social acceptability and preferences of CCUS using CFB-CaL as CO₂ capture technology”.

Systematic Reviews (SRs) are a consistent, transparent and widely used methodology to identify, analyse and interpret the existing evidence from multiple disciplines, relying on different methodologies and focusing on different geographic and temporal contexts (Peñasco et al 2021). They are often used to inform further research and policy decisions (Haddaway and Pullin 2014).

Using an SR, this deliverable delves into the existing literature on social acceptability of CCUS technologies to try to answer the following three questions: 1) What has been the level of knowledge/awareness of CCUS technologies in the past worldwide?; 2) What has been the social acceptability of these technologies?; 3) What factors (enablers/drivers and barriers) influence the social acceptability of CCUS? A crucial distinction in this context is between local acceptance (local residents of an area where a specific project is implemented) and social acceptability (the wider socio-political acceptance of a technology, as defined in Grashof, 2019).

In order to answer those questions, a systematic review protocol has been adopted, which is explained in detail in the following section 2. The results of the systematic review are provided in section 3. The main findings related to the aforementioned three questions are discussed in section 4. Section 5 concludes this report.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 WHAT IS A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW?

A systematic literature review was conducted in order to identify relevant literature and accurately represent the state of academic research on CCS’ social acceptability.

According to Denyer and Tranfield (2009, p.671), a systematic review (SR) is “a specific methodology that locates existing studies, selects and evaluates contributions, analyses and synthesizes data, and reports the evidence in such a way that allows reasonably clear conclusions to be reached about what is and is not known”. Its aim is to provide “a comprehensive, unbiased and replicable summary of the state of knowledge on a well-defined issue” (Sovacool et al 2018, p.22). In the realm of energy studies, systematic reviews have increasingly been performed (see, e.g., Peñasco et al 2021, Grubb et al 2021, del Río and Kiefer 2022 and 2023). To the best of our knowledge, they have not been used to analyse the social acceptability of CCUS technologies.

2.2 Why a systematic review?

We apply a systematic review because it is regarded as the best way to perform literature reviews, since they have more rigor than narrative reviews (Sovacool et al 2018). Khan et al (2003, p.118) even argue that “reviews should never be done in any other way”. An SR provides a meticulous summary of the available research in response to a research questions, adopting a holistic view and often yielding new insights. As stressed by Peñasco et al (2021, supplementary material p.1) “a systematic review allows us to summarize and analyse the available, and often contradictory literature without imposing constraints on the use of one specific methodology. In addition, performing a systematic review allows the integration of research from multiple disciplines and helps identify and assess, in a reproducible way, the evidence available to understand the state of knowledge regarding the relationship between a policy instrument and an outcome”.

An SR is different from a narrative review in the traditional sense, because it is “a self-contained research project in itself that explores a clearly specified question, usually derived from a policy or practice problem, using existing studies” (Denyer and Tranfield 2009, p.671). An SR also differs from other review methods because it should adhere to a strict protocol and follow distinct and exacting principles. “For example, in an SR, the researcher is required to set prespecified relevance and quality criteria for the selection/inclusion of studies and to make such criteria transparent to readers” (Denyer and Tranfield 2009, p.671).

The following Box 1 synthesises the advantages, drawbacks and limitations of SRs, and also discusses when they should and should not be used.

Box 1. Advantages and Limitations of Systematic Reviews

Advantages

Compared to a typical narrative review, an SR uses an explicit and replicable research design, ensures comprehensiveness in the literature search, and reduces bias in the selection of studies.

Drawbacks and limitations

SRs are resource-intensive and time-consuming, focus upon a narrow range of questions, are biased towards quantitative research methodologies, are unsuitable for addressing complex problems and policies, use an “additive” approach to synthesis that neglects the complementary nature of different studies and its narrow scope may prevent more in-depth insights. SRs may suffer from bias, i.e., the researcher’s selection of criteria and concepts critically influences the inclusion and coding of articles.

When should SRs be used?

SRs can be applied to topics where both quantitative and qualitative evidence is relevant, experiments (true or quasi) may or may not be feasible, researchers are concerned with “what works” in what context, and multiple and competing factors are at play.

It is particularly suitable to comprehensively summarize and interpret large bodies of quantitative or qualitative evidence on well-defined research questions.

When shouldn't SRs be used?

When sufficient time and resources are not available, fields where evidence is sparse or patchy and in the case of multidimensional problems (rather than narrow questions).

Source: own elaboration based on Sovacool et al (2018).

There have been previous reviews of CCUS, but they did not follow a systematic approach (L'Orange et al 2014, Witte 2021, Tcvetkov et al 2019, Nielsen et al 2022 and Jones et al 2017). The closest to this review is Tcvetkov et al (2019), which is quite comprehensive in the consideration of different drivers and barriers of CCUS. Tcvetchow et al (2019) review 135 articles related to the public perception of CCS technology. Nine factors that influence public perception

of CCS were identified for the analysis¹. It shows in an Appendix whether a selection of the reviewed articles considers these factors, i.e., the distribution of factors by the articles. However, it provides a very general picture, without disaggregating specific factors into the subfactors which are really the relevant issue for the analysis of the determinants of social acceptability and questionnaire design.

Our review is complementary to Tcvetkov et al (2019), but it is updated, provides more detail on some aspects (scope, content and methodology) and focuses on the different factors positively and negatively affecting the social acceptability of CCUS, considering a lower level of granularity of these factors. The review of Tcvetkov et al (2019) only covers the period until 2018 and misses 17 relevant articles. It has a narrower focus (factors influencing the social acceptability of CCS with surveys), but a more systematic and deeper analysis of drivers/enablers and barriers to CCS acceptability. We also pay attention to the stage of the CCUS being analysed and the data treatment methods used in each article.

2.3 How was our systematic review carried out?

Systematic reviews are performed in a sequence of stages. For example, in its guidelines for evidence synthesis, Pullin et al (2018) propose three stages of review: search strategy, screening and data extraction. This is also the protocol followed by Grubb et al (2021). Sovacool et al (2018) recommend the following phases: (1) crafting of explicit research questions; (2) systematically searching the available literature using defined search terms; (3) using explicit criteria for including or excluding studies; (4) determining and then executing a coding strategy or analytical protocol; and (5) analyzing or synthesizing the collected evidence. We follow this 5-stage procedure. These authors recommend to use a code of practice to carry out literature reviews which we have followed: 1) Be as explicit as possible about the process of the review you use, explaining your rationale and approach; 2) be transparent: if applicable, report the sources/databases covered, the dates and time period examined, the search term(s) used, the languages searched, and whether any sampling of results was done (if the population of articles was too large). Accordingly, a step-by-step approach, as required in systematic reviews, was followed in this report (Box 2).

Box 2. The step-by-step approach followed in the systematic review of CCUS social acceptability

- 1) Definition of search strategy for the systematic review, with a definition of the aim of the systematic review and inclusion and exclusion criteria.
- 2) Searches in Web of Science (WoS) and Scopus databases (initial selection) plus manual searches plus snowballing in references of existing journals.
- 3) Screening: Application of the exclusion/inclusion criteria to the title and abstract (final selection).
- 4) Content analysis (coding).
- 5) Analyzing and synthesizing the collected evidence.

1) Definition of the search strategy.

The aim of this review was to search for contributions on the drivers/enablers and barriers to the social acceptability of CCUS, considering acceptability in its broader sense (general/international/national/regional/local). The aim is to answer the following three questions:

- What has been the level of knowledge/awareness of CCUS technologies in the past worldwide?;
- What has been the social acceptability of these technologies?;
- What factors (enablers/drivers and barriers) influence the social acceptability of CCUS?

To this end, a comprehensive search strategy was defined and operationalised with two complementary searches based on keywords covering CCUS social acceptability.

Some authors distinguish between "perception": the cognitive process to perceive, recognize, and to be aware of something, (in this study, we define "technology perceptions" as individual assessments of (dis)advantages and risks, associated with a technology, its infrastructures, processes, products, and usage contexts, that – among other factors - influence and form acceptance) and "acceptance": a positive attitude (approval) or supporting behaviour (e.g.,

¹ These factors were: Kn – Knowledge; Acc – Acceptance of CCS and preference between technologies; BR - Benefits and Risks perception; GovS - Governmental Policy and Interaction between Stakeholders; SD - Socio-demographic factors; Tr – Trust, Aw – Awareness and Will - Willingness to pay).

proclaiming, purchase, usage) of the development and implementation or usage of technologies and products (Offermann-van Heek et al 2020). Our analysis focuses on acceptance. In addition, acceptance can be analysed at a general level ("are you in favour of CCS to mitigate climate change?") or within a given geographical scope, which can be broad, such as the national level ("are you in favour of the implementation of CCS in your country?") or at a more regional or local level ("are you in favour of the implementation of CCS in your region or municipality?"). These review questions follow the CIMO logic (see below).

2) Searches.

Searches in Clarivate's WoS and Elsevier's Scopus databases were performed and results from them were merged. These databases include extensive collections of academic literature suitable to conduct systematic literature reviews and bibliometric studies. Often, due to the technical impossibility to merge the results from WoS and Scopus (Kumar Kar & Harichandan, 2022), only one database has been used by researchers for these kinds of studies, but it is estimated that this would lead to the loss of up to 50% of potentially relevant literature (Chistov et al., 2021), which would jeopardize the validity of the corresponding studies (Kumar Kar & Harichandan, 2022). Specifically, the search was carried out in those two databases by applying the search terms to title, abstract and keywords in October 2022.

A broad criterion was used, i.e., the potentially relevant contributions were not included from the start by making them visible in the search. The approach was rather to be as comprehensive as possible in the potential contributions that could be *a priori* relevant, and decide at a later step whether the studies were indeed pertinent for the analysis of the social acceptability of CCUS and, in particular, of the drivers and barriers to such acceptability.

We defined the following inclusion and exclusion criteria for our search on the drivers and barriers to the social acceptability of CCUS (box 3).

Box 3. Inclusion and exclusion criteria

- Interviewees: Common people.
- Stages of CCUS. Broad technological coverage: capture, transport, storage and utilisation.
- Geographical scope: Worldwide.
- Temporal scope: 2002-2022.
- Acceptance scope: general and local.
- Scientific journal articles in English.
- Data collection method: quantitative data gathered in surveys.
- Transnationally, nationally, regionally and locally representative.
- No restrictions on sample size n.
- The articles have to report on the statistical method used to treat the data. Statistical inference treatment is not required to be part of our review, but at least descriptive statistics is.

Some of the above choices need to be justified. The review did not impose any geographical or temporal constraints, and only journal articles published in English have been included. Books, book chapters, dissertations/theses, conference papers or working papers were excluded. It is assumed that journal articles are the ones meeting the rigorous peer-review requirement as they have passed the review procedures in the journal/editor board of publication (Peñasco et al., 2021).

By exclusively focusing on survey analysis and results, we focus on the views of common people, i.e., not experts, industry representatives or other stakeholders, and on the empirical analysis of CCUS drivers and barriers, i.e., focus groups, Delphi studies, exploratory or conceptual approaches were excluded. The reason is to "let the data speak", i.e., to benefit from quantitative data on the drivers and barriers to CCUS acceptability gathered in surveys. There are several reasons to exclude studies which use focus groups: 1) the aforementioned reviews include them; 2) more importantly, this review is instrumental for task 6.2.2, which will design and apply a survey to assess the social acceptability of CCUS in a case study; 3) studies using surveys already consider the insights from focus groups, i.e., a survey is not carried out from scratch, but the surveys elaborated draw strongly from the findings in case studies². Therefore, the surveys already include the knowledge and insights gathered through focus groups.

² Indeed, this separation between qualitative and quantitative approaches can be deemed a bit artificial, since each feeds the other.

The articles have to report on the statistical method used to treat the data. Not necessarily statistical inference treatment is required in order to be part of our review, but at least the articles should use descriptive statistics to report the data. Many of those studies included in our review statistically analyze the relationship between the factors and social acceptability with inferential analysis, although even when done using inferential statistical techniques, care should be taken not to assume causality, since usually only correlation can be inferred. However, many of those studies only use descriptive statistics. The studies considered in this review are not necessarily nationally representative, i.e., they could be transnationally (two countries or more), regionally (a region within a country) or locally representative (only the area where the project is implemented). All these types of studies are included in this report. Also, a large sample size was not a requirement to be included in this report. The article with the lowest sample size was Sun et al 2020, with n=60.

Based on these inclusion/exclusion criteria, the search in those two databases was actually performed. In order to take into account the different versions of "accept" ("accept", "acceptance", "acceptability", "accepting", etc.) in those two searches, the operator "*" has been used. Therefore, the following search query was adopted:

Topic = (CCS OR CCUS) AND Topic = (social AND (*accept* OR *reject*))

Topic = title, abstract, keywords

Then, in both searches, filters were applied:

In WoS:

- Categories: The usual categories in our field of research (i.e. "energy and fuels") + categories in psychology + categories in sociology (there were very few publications in these two categories).
- Language = english.
- Type: all types, including papers, review papers and conference papers.

In Scopus:

- Categories: The usual categories in our field of research.
- Language = English.
- Type: all types (2 books and book chapters were excluded).

The findings from the databases were complemented with several complementary searches. A journal-by-journal analysis was carried out, looking in the search engines of key energy and environmental journals (IJGGC, Energy Policy, Energy Journal, Energy Economics, Journal of Cleaner Production, Nature Climate Change, Nature Energy, Environmental Innovation and Sustainable transitions, Climate Policy, Energy Research and Social Science and Mitigation and Adaptation Strategies for Global Change). In addition, reading the selected articles led to a few more articles being found since they were referenced in these articles.

3) Screening.

Then, a screening of those articles was performed. This process was a sequential one and a conservative approach was followed, i.e. we were extremely cautious not to discard papers which could be relevant for our purposes³. First, we looked at the title of the article and, when it was clear that the article was out of the scope of this review, it was excluded from it. If the title suggested that the article could be relevant in this context, it was included in the review (although "put on hold" pending its full reading). For those cases for which we had doubts with respect to the title, we read the abstract and followed the same procedure. In case of doubt when reading the abstract, we read the whole article and decided accordingly. This led to the final selection of articles.

The following Box 4 mentions the specific reasons to exclude articles which had been identified in our Scopus and WoS database searches.

³ This is also the approach followed in other SRs. For example, Grubb et al (2021, p.7) argue that, "in cases of uncertainty, a precautionary approach was taken and articles were retained to the next stage".

Box 4. Specific reasons for exclusion of articles from the database searches

- It is merely a theoretical paper.
- It is a methodological paper.
- It is a qualitative case study.
- It is a review of previous studies.
- The paper is unrelated to social acceptability.
- The paper is merely about ethical attitudes.
- The article is not about social acceptability as such, but about instruments to improve social acceptability of CCUS and information provision on CCUS.
- The paper does not contain original research.
- The study is not about acceptability but about perception of benefits and disadvantages of CCS and questions about the survey itself and there isn't any statistical analysis.
- There isn't any empirical analysis.
- The methodology of the paper is not clear.
- The paper is a stakeholder analysis.
- The paper uses stakeholder interviews and focus groups.
- The paper uses a survey of experts.
- The paper is a media analysis.
- It is a paper which analyses the applicability of CCS research to bioenergy carbon capture and storage (BECCS).
- The paper focuses on the drivers and barriers to CCUS, social acceptability being only one among many other factors.
- The paper is about barriers to CCUS in general, not only (or specifically) about social acceptability.
- This is a study on the perception of CCUS managers.
- It is a study on the implications of other energy projects for CCUS.
- This is about the stance of non-governmental organisations (NGOs) towards CCUS.
- It is a study about the factors which contribute to the sustainability of CCUS projects, including social acceptability.
- This is not an empirical study, but one which predicts the possible effect of CCUS on social acceptability on the basis of the psychometric theory of public risk perception.

It could be argued that more emphasis should be put on recent studies than on older ones, given that the acceptability of CCUS can be expected to be influenced by the characteristics of the technology itself (the more mature and less expensive is a technology, the more it is accepted) and also by the context conditions (e.g., the urgency of addressing the climate mitigation problem, concern on the security of energy supply in a context of higher penetration of variable renewables and tensions in the gas market...). However, this has not been done because there is not a clear temporal threshold from which we could consider that social acceptance of CCUS may have shifted for common people. In addition, this potential shifting may not have been produced yet or may have been produced in different years for different regions/countries. A weighting on the academic relevance of each paper was not done either, as many publications are very recent and, thus, have not been able to accumulate many citations.

4) Content analysis (coding).

All the initial sources were fully read with two purposes: i) to confirm that the article should be part of the review, given that it was in line with its aim; ii) to extract relevant insights on the articles regarding:

- general information on the article: authors, title, year of publication, scope, aim and methods (both of data collection, including sample size, and of data treatment).
- Results regarding the awareness/knowledge of CCUS.
- Results regarding the social acceptability of CCUS.
- Results regarding the drivers/enablers and barriers to the social acceptability of CCUS.

It is standard practice to extract relevant information from the articles and include it in tables (Cohen and Tubb 2018, Pullin et al 2018, Grubb et al 2021). Therefore, four tables (Tables 1-4) for each of those four issues were built and filled in Microsoft Word (.docx), in a very time-intensive process.

Given the research question(s) proposed in this task, applying the Context-Intervention-Mechanisms-Outcomes (CIMO) framework, devised by Denyer and Tranfield (2009), seems particularly pertinent. The CIMO framework is a structured and contextual approach widely used for systematic literature reviews in social sciences. It helps to define the scope of the study and frame the research question in SRs and to turn such research question into the searches needed for databases and search engines (see Booth 2021, Denyer and Tranfield 2009, and CQUniversity Library 2023, for details). The following Table 1 summarises the different elements/components of the CIMO framework.

Table 1. Elements/components of the CIMO framework.

Element/component	Questions asked
Context	Which individuals, relationships, institutional settings, or wider systems are you focusing on? Who are the individuals of interest? What interpersonal relationships are of interest? Which aspects of the institutional setting are of interest? What aspects of the wider infrastructural system are of interest?
Intervention	What is the intervention of interest? The effects of what event, action, or activity are being studied?
Mechanisms	Why are mechanisms activated or not activated? What are the mechanisms that explain the relationship between interventions and outcomes? Under what circumstances are these mechanisms activated or not activated? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Which responses to the intervention explain how it leads to the outcome? • Which circumstances cause these responses? • In which circumstances are these responses avoided?
Outcomes	What are the effects of the intervention that we focus on? How will the outcomes be measured? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Which effects of the intervention you have chosen to focus on? • How are you defining and measuring these effects?

Source: Source: Denyer and Tranfield (2009, p.283), Booth et al (2021), CQUniversity Library (2023).

5) Analyzing and synthesizing the collected evidence.

We analysed the direction of the impact and the level of agreement and evidence. Regarding the former, for each article, we identified which factors had either a positive (+), negative (-), no relationship (=) or unclear relationship (?) with the social acceptability of CCUS. In addition, we identified the level of evidence and agreement between the different articles on the direction of the effects of each factor. The results are reported in section 4.3.

Once all the tables were filled, we aggregated the results and the analysis was performed based on those aggregated numbers, reaching relevant insights and conclusions on each of the four aforementioned CIMO bullet points.

3 RESULTS OF THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW

3.1 Final selection of articles.

The first search in the WoS led to 154 references, whereas 175 documents were found using the Scopus database. When filters were applied (publication type and language), 144 and 133 publications resulted respectively. Identification of 78 duplicates between the two searches led to 199 publications. After screening and applying the other exclusion criteria, 42 articles were within the scope of our review. The manual searches and snowballing led to 29 additional publications with a final outcome of 71 publications.

Table 2. Final selection of articles

	Web of Science (WoS)	Scopus
Search queries	154	175
Application of filters	144	133
Aggregated result	277	
Identification of duplicates	78	
Total number of documents pre-screening	199	
Total number of articles after screening	42	
+ articles from manual search (+snowballing)	29	
Final outcome (individual publications)	71	

Table 3 shows the list of articles finally included in the revision.

Table 3. Articles finally included in the review

Article (first author/year/journal)	Temporal and geographical scope
Palmgren et al. (2004)	2003, U.S.
Itaoka et al. (2005)	2003, Japan
Shackley et al. (2005)	2003, U.K.
Huijts et al. (2007)	2003, the Netherlands
Miller et al. (2007)	2005, Australia
Tokushige et al. (2007a)	2004-2005, Japan
Tokushige et al. (2007b)	2003-2004 Japan
de Best-Waldhober et al. (2009)	2004, the Netherlands
Ha-Duong et al. (2009)	2007, France
Itaoka et al. (2009)	2007, Japan
Midden and Huijts (2009)	2003, the Netherlands
Sharp et al. (2009)	2005, Canada
Duan (2010)	2009, China
Wallquist et al. (2010)	2009, Switzerland

Amikawa et al. (2011)	2010, Australia, Japan, Taiwan, Korea, Norway, U.K., U.S.
Itaoka et al. (2011)	2003 and 2007, Japan
L'Orange et al. (2011)	2010, Switzerland
Pietzner et al. (2011)	2009-2010. Germany, Greece, the Netherlands, Norway, Romania, U.K.
de Best-Waldhober et al. (2012)	2006, The Netherlands
Kraeusel and Möst (2012)	2011, Germany
Moutenet et al. (2012)	2010 and 2011, Quebec (Canada)
Oltra et al. (2012)	2010, Spain
Terwel and Daamen (2012)	2010, the Netherlands.
Terwel et al. (2012)	2010, the Netherlands
Wallquist et al. (2012)	2011, Switzerland
Brunsting et al. (2013)	2011, Poland and Scotland
Steeper (2013)	2006, 2011, Australia
Dowd et al. (2014)	2013, Australia, the Netherlands, Japan
Dütschke et al. (2014)	2013, Germany
Kaiser et al. (2014)	2012, Poland
Krause et al. (2014)	2011, Indiana (U.S.)
Li et al. (2014)	2013, China
L'Orange et al. (2014)	2012, Canada
Schumann et al. (2014)	2013, Germany
Toma et al. (2014)	2011, European Union (12 countries)
Warren et al. (2014)	2011, Indiana (U.S.)
Chen et al. (2015)	2013, China
Broecks et al. (2016)	2015, the Netherlands
Dütschke et al. (2016)	2013, Germany
Karimi et al. (2016)	2011, 12 European countries
Yang et al. (2016)	2014, China
Boyd et al. (2017)	2010, Canada

Braun (2017)	2013, Germany
Perdan et al. (2017)	2015, U.K.
Schumann (2017)	2013, Germany
Braun et al. (2018)	2013, Germany
Karimi and Tikka (2018)	2011, 12 European countries
Offerman-van Heek et al. (2018)	2016, Germany
Arning et al. (2019)	2017, Germany
Ashworth et al. (2019)	2017, Australia, China
Linzenich et al. (2019)	2017, Germany
Saito et al. (2019)	2015, Japan
Shah et al. (2019)	2019, Texas
Wang et al. (2019)	2018, China
Whitmarsh et al. (2019)	2017, U.K., U.S., Canada, Norway, the Netherlands.
Wolske et al. (2019)	2017, U.S.
Arning et al. (2020)	2017, Germany
Cox et al. (2020)	2019, U.S. and U.K.
Moon et al. (2020)	2017, Texas (US)
Offerman-van Heek et al. (2020)	2018, Germany
Sun et al. (2020)	2019, China
Broecks et al. (2021)	2019, U.K. and the Netherlands
Ferguson and Ashworth (2021)	2017, Australia
Lima et al. (2021)	2020, Brazil
Linzenich et al. (2021)	2020, Germany
Pianta et al. (2021)	2018, U.S.
Wang et al. (2021)	2019, China
Koukoulzas et al. (2022)	2022, Europe
Merk et al. (2022)	2019, Germany and Norway.
Shah et al. (2023)	2021, US

3.2 Journals

57% of the articles reviewed were concentrated in 4 journals, but many journals have only one contribution.

Figure 1. Distribution of the selected articles across journals (number of articles).

3.3 Surveys over the years

There seems to be a concentration of studies in the middle of the period (i.e., between 2010 and 2013). However, no discernable pattern over time can be observed (i.e., no time trend).

Figure 2. Year of publication of the selected articles (number of articles).

3.4 Geographical distribution

A strong geographical concentration can also be observed. Three countries (Germany, the U.S. and the Netherlands) account for about half of the studies.

Figure 3. Geographical scope of the selected articles. * One study for the following 7 countries Brazil, France, Greece, Korea, Romania, Spain and Taiwan.

3.5 Stage analysed

The whole CCS steps are covered in most articles. However, there is a very limited coverage of single stages, in particular CCU, which has not received much attention in the empirical literature on CCS acceptability so far.

Figure 4. Number of articles focusing on each stage of CCS.

3.6 Acceptability focus settings

Most papers have focused on general acceptability and acceptance at the national level. Local acceptability has received less attention. Acceptability at the regional or international level (i.e. comparisons across countries) have received scant attention.

Figure 5. Acceptability according to the settings (number of papers).

3.7 Source of survey data

On-line surveys account for most of the data (33), followed by paper-and-pencil (17) and telephone surveys (8).

Figure 6. Source of survey data (number of papers). * This includes three papers which use the Eurobarometer (based on face-to-face interviews)

3.8 Sample size

There is a wide variability in the size of the samples, from 60 to almost 14.000 respondents. Most studies are concentrated in the segment of 900 to 2.000 respondents.

Figure 7. Sample sizes in the reviewed articles. Note: y-axis = number of respondents; x-axis = article number.

3.9 Method type

Regarding the method type, descriptive statistics and multiple regression analysis (often with ordinary least squares) are the most common methods to treat the data. Note that, similarly to Peñasco et al (2021), we classify each paper according to its method, but we do not attempt to evaluate how well the particular method was implemented. Instead, we rely on the assumption that the peer-reviewed published publications we include in our systematic review are qualitatively satisfactory as they have passed the review procedures in the journal/editor board of publication.

Figure 8. Method types. ANCOVA=Analysis of covariance ; ANOVA=Analysis of variance; PCA=Principal components analysis.

4 MAIN FINDINGS

4.1 CCUS knowledge/awareness

Questions on the previous knowledge of CCUS were asked in many surveys, but not in all the studies in this review. Questions were asked in different ways, which limits the comparability of the results from different surveys. In some of them, only a YES/NO answer to that question was possible, whereas, in others, respondents could report on their different degrees of CCUS knowledge. For example, in Whitmarsh et al (2019), respondents were asked to identify their level of knowledge in a scale from “do not know anything about CCS” to “know a lot”. In other surveys, knowledge about CCUS was compared to knowledge about other energy technologies, as in Li et al (2014) and Ashworth et al (2019). In Broecks et al (2021), respondents were asked whether they had heard of CCS and whether they knew hardly anything about it rather than quite a bit about it. In Yang et al (2016), 65% of respondents had never heard about CCS and 29.1% had heard about it but don’t know very well. In Ha-Duong et al (2009), only 6% of respondents were able to provide a satisfactory definition of the technology. In L’Orange et al (2014), 91% of respondents correctly answered the open question about the purpose of CCS⁴.

The following table includes the results for those studies which asked respondents to provide an answer to their level of knowledge/awareness of CCUS.

Table 4. Results (I). Knowledge and awareness of CCUS in the reviewed literature

Article (first author/year)	Knowledge/awareness of CCUS
Itaoka et al. (2005)	31% were familiar with CCS. This exceeded those who stated familiarity with iron fertilization (18%) but was less than familiarity with bio-energy/biomass (52%). Of all ten types of technologies, the respondents were most familiar with solar energy with almost all (97%) stating some level of awareness of it.
Shackley et al. (2005)	None (0%) of the respondents were familiar with CCS prior to the interview.
Huijts et al. (2007)	Before reading the information, 76% indicated to know nothing to very little about CCS, while 21% knew a little and 3% indicated to have a fair amount of knowledge. Nobody indicated to know a lot about the topic.
de Best-Waldhober et al. (2009)	The majority of respondents stated either not to be aware of CCS in general (76.1%), or just a bit (20.2%). The majority of respondents reported not to have heard of most CCS technologies.
Ha-Duong et al. (2009)	About 6% of respondents were able to provide a satisfactory definition of the technology. Geological CO ₂ storage or sequestration was clearly a technology most people had never heard about. Only 34% had heard about CO ₂ storage and only 27% had heard about CO ₂ sequestration.
Itaoka et al. (2009)	9% of respondents (general public in Tokyo and Sapporo) knew to some extent about CCS and another 22% reported that they have heard of it (the respective rates in the door-to-door survey were 7% and 12% and 18% and 33% for the Internet survey).
Midden and Huijts (2009)	97% and 84% of participants indicated knowing little to nothing about CO ₂ storage before the information was given as well as afterwards (respectively).
Sharp et al. (2009)	Knowledge of CCS among survey respondents was low: 10.5% and 15.4% of the Canada (CAN) and Alberta and Saskatchewan (AB/SK) sub-samples respectively. Only 5.6% and 6.2% of the CAN and AB/SK sub-samples respectively were able to correctly identify that CCS addressed climate change, with respondents more likely to believe that CCS was a solution for the hole in the ozone layer
Duan (2010)	Only 24% of the Chinese respondents knew about CCS technology to some extent.

⁴ This was so if they mentioned the mitigation of climate change, environmental protection, the permanent storage of CO₂, the reduction of CO₂ emissions into the atmosphere, or similar reasons.

Wallquist et al. (2010)	30% of the respondents had heard about CCS before.
L'Orange et al. (2011)	74% percent reported that they had never heard of CCS before, 22% indicated they had heard "a little", and only 4% had heard "a lot" about it.
Pietzner et al. (2011)	60% of all respondents indicated to have never heard about CCS before participating in this study. The public awareness of CCS in the six European countries was quite different (from 75% in Romania to 37% in Norway).
Moutenet et al. (2012)	Only 13% of respondents in 2011 (14% in 2010) said that they had already heard of CCS in the region. These results were similar to the national average, which was 17% in 2010
Terwel et al. (2012)	Public awareness of the CCS plan in the Barendrecht region (the Netherlands): only few answered that they had "never heard" about the plan (3% of the respondents). The vast majority stated to know "a little" (48% of the respondents) or "quite a lot" (49% of the respondents) about the plan.
Brunsting et al. (2013)	Awareness of CCS was much lower in Poland than in Scotland: of the Polish participants, 27% reported to have heard of CCS in general and 15% reported to have heard of local CCS. Of the Scottish respondents, 57% reported to have heard of CCS in general and 46% reported to have heard of local CCS.
Steeper (2013)	In their survey in Australia, only 32 % had heard of geosequestration in 2006 (the term used then which has now been replaced by CCS). Of those who were aware of the technology, 55 % claimed they had very little knowledge about what it actually involved. 81 % had not heard about the proposed Otway Project. Awareness of CCS as a technology more than doubled from 2006 to 2011 (from 32% to 69%). Awareness of the Otway Project also increased significantly across the region, from 18% in 2006 to 63% in 2011. Local communities were much more likely to be aware of the project (76% vs. 52% in Warrnambool).
Dowd et al. (2014)	CO ₂ was moderate to poorly understood by many participants across all three countries.
Dütschke et al. (2014)	6.8% of participants reported to feel well-informed about CCS, 36.4% had heard about it and 56.8% knew nothing about CCS.
Kaiser et al. (2014)	The results of the representative survey of people living in the Załęcze-Żuchłów region (Poland) showed that awareness of CCS in general and of CCS plans for the region was very low. 62% of the participants indicated that they had never heard about CCS in general and 78% stated they had not heard of any local CCS plans (21% had heard of local CCS; 1% answered "don't know").
Li et al. (2014)	CCUS was the most unfamiliar technology for the respondents amongst climate change mitigation technologies. 57.2% of respondents did not know what CCUS was. The public awareness of CCUS (such as pros and cons) was quite unclear. In the survey, the target respondents were asked which environment issues could be solved by CCUS. A large number of people could not make a judgment or gave wrong answers.
Schumann et al. (2014)	50% of the respondents nationwide had heard of the "storage of CO ₂ in onshore repositories" and the "storage of CO ₂ under the seabed", respectively. However, the percentage of citizens nationwide who answered that they knew "quite a bit or a lot" about CO ₂ storage was low. Only 9.7%, 6.6% and 4.5% of respondents heard about storage of CO ₂ in on-shore repositories, storage of CO ₂ under the seabed and CCS, respectively, and knew quite a bit about them.
Chen et al. (2015)	61.7% of respondents did not know what CCS is. CCS was the most unfamiliar technology for the respondents amongst the climate change-mitigation technologies.
Dütschke et al. (2016)	Only a few respondents indicated they felt well informed about CCS (6.8%), but most participants knew nothing about CCS (56.8%), or only had heard of it (36.4%).
Yang et al. (2016)	65% of respondents had never heard about CCS in China and 29.1% had heard about it but didn't know very well.
Perdan et al. (2017)	There was a very low level of public awareness of CCU: only 9% of the respondents expressed confidence in knowing what it was.

Schumann (2017)	The level of factual knowledge about pipelines among the German public was very low (37% to 48% do not know).
Braun et al. (2018)	The majority of the respondents had at least heard a little about CCS (52%).
Offerman-van Heek et al. (2018)	Concerning previous experiences with CCU, only 18.9% of the sample indicated that they had already heard of the term "carbon capture & utilization". When asked for perceived knowledge on CCU, 46.5% of participants indicated to feel "very badly" informed about CCU, 24.4% felt "badly" and 19.7% "rather badly" informed. Only 7.1% reported to feel "rather well", 1.6% "well" and 0.8% "very well" informed about CCU.
Arning et al. (2019)	The majority (75%) of the sample reported to feel (very) uninformed about CCS and CCU and the respective process-chain steps. Only 8–10% of respondents rated their perceived information level as high to very high. The knowledge about CCS and CCU in the sample was on comparably low levels.
Ashworth et al. (2019)	When respondents were asked to rate their knowledge of 12 energy technologies (1=no knowledge to 7=expert knowledge), respondents in the Chinese sample were more likely to rate their knowledge higher than in the Australian sample. Respondents in both countries indicated they had the lowest level of knowledge about CCS and biomass (averages for CCS: Australia = 2.5, China= 3.0).
Saito et al. (2019)	57% of all respondents answered "No, I have never heard about CCS", 33% answered "I have heard about it before" and 9% responded "I know about it".
Wang et al. (2019)	59% of interviewees had never heard of CCS and 36% had heard but did not really know.
Whitmarsh et al. (2019)	Public awareness of CCS was low, although there were cross-national differences in awareness. Respondents in the Norway sample showed the highest levels of awareness (9% did not know anything about CCS, and 9% knew a lot) and the US respondents had the lowest level (38% did not know anything about CCS, and 12% knew a lot).
Cox et al. (2020)	Only 9.6% (United States) and 5.7% (United Kingdom) of respondents said they knew "a great deal" or "a fair amount" about carbon dioxide removal.
Broecks et al. (2021)	Most respondents in the survey had heard of CCS (64.2%), but most respondents indicated that they knew hardly anything about it (52.9%) rather than quite a bit about it (11.3%).
Lima et al. (2021)	CCS was mostly ignored by the sample respondents in Brazil: 78% in Sao Mateus and 82% in Vitoria. Only 5% of respondents in Sao Mateus and 2% in Vitoria mentioned that they understood CCS, but only 0.5% of the total interviewed answered it correctly.
Linzenich et al. (2021)	6.8% of the sample felt very well or well informed about CCU, whereas the majority felt (rather) uninformed.
Wang et al. (2021)	5% stated that they had some knowledge about CCS before the survey, 36% had heard about CCS (but know little about it) and 59% had never heard about CCS.
Merk et al. (2022)	Only 15% of Norwegian respondents reported that they have never heard about CCS and 26% mentioned that they knew a lot about it. These percentages were 63% and 6% in Germany, respectively.

Source: Own elaboration. Note: Only those articles which report data on CCS knowledge/awareness are included.

Some main insights and stylized facts can be inferred from the studies reviewed regarding different themes relevant for CCUS acceptability.

- *General knowledge levels for CCS are low.*

Given the aforementioned methodological differences across studies, an overall, aggregated and comparative picture of the results of different studies cannot be provided. However, some general insights can still be provided.

Overall, the level of knowledge on CCS appears to be low within the group of respondents, with the exceptions of Japan and Norway. Between 2% and 11% know the technology (with the exception of Japan, where 31% were familiar

with CCS) and between 56% and 97% do not know anything (with the exception of Norway, which is clearly an outlier since only 15% of Norwegian respondents report that they have never heard about CCS).

Respondents were sometimes asked if they knew much about CCS and, in case they stated "Yes", a "check question" was asked to prove that they did not know much. For example, in Lima et al (2021), 5% of respondents in Sao Mateus and 2% in Vitoria mentioned that they understood CCS, but only 0.5% of the total interviewed people answered correctly the "check question".

- *CCS is one of the least well-known energy technologies.*

Compared to other energy technologies, CCS is the least well-known. For example, in Ashworth et al (2019) respondents in Australia and China indicated they had the least level of knowledge about CCS and biomass (averages for CCS: Australia = 2.5, China = 3.0). In Japan, Itaoka et al (2005) found that 31% of respondents were familiar with CCS. This exceeded those who stated familiarity with iron fertilization (18%) but was less than that for bio-energy/biomass (52%). Of all ten types of technologies, the respondents were most familiar with solar energy with almost all (97%) stating some level of awareness of it. Chen et al (2015) found that CCS was the most unfamiliar technology for the respondents among the climate change-mitigation technologies in China.

- *Strong cross-country differences exist.*

Cross-country differences in the awareness of CCS are seldom explored but, when done, the results show that these are significant. For example, Brunsting et al (2013) compared Poland and Scotland in this context. 27% of the Polish participants reported to have heard of CCS in general and 15% reported to have heard of local CCS. 57% of the Scottish respondents reported to have heard of CCS in general and 46% reported to have heard of local CCS. These percentages show that awareness of CCS was much lower in Poland than in Scotland. In Broecks et al (2021), crosstab analyses were used to test for differences in CCS awareness between the Netherlands and U.K. Awareness of CCS was found to be somewhat higher in the Netherlands than in the UK. In Merk et al (2022), only 15% of Norwegian respondents reported that they had never heard about CCS and 26% mentioned that they knew a lot about it. These percentages were 63% and 6% in Germany, respectively. In Pietzner et al (2011), 60% of all respondents indicated to have never heard about CCS before participating in this study, but the public awareness of CCS in the six European countries was quite different, ranging from 75% in Romania to 37% in Norway.

- *Considerable differences in geographical acceptability focus exist, with local knowledge of CCS often being higher than in general knowledge studies.*

There are strong differences between general, national and local studies, with local knowledge being usually greater than awareness at the national level. This is a logical finding, since proximity plays an important role. For example, in Terwell et al (2012), public awareness of the CCS plan was assessed by asking respondents whether they knew about the plan to capture, transport, and store CO₂ in the Barendrecht region (the Netherlands). Only 3% answered that they had "never heard" about the plan. The vast majority stated to know "a little" (48% of the respondents) or "quite a lot" (49% of the respondents) about the plan.

In their analysis in the context of the Otway project in Australia, Steeper (2013) found that the local community was more likely to be aware of CCS than the regional community (73% vs. 64%). Those in the local community who claimed they had some or detailed knowledge of CCS also increased from 34% to 66%. Awareness of the Otway Project also increased significantly across the region, from 18% in 2006 to 63% in 2011. Again, local communities were much more likely to be aware of the project (76% vs. 52% in Warrnambool).

- *Differences between stages, with "storage" being the better known and "utilisation" being the least well-known.*

Not all the stages in CCUS are equally well-known. Within the generally low awareness level, "storage" is more well-known than "utilisation". For example, Offerman-van Heek et al (2018) found that only 7.1% of respondents reported to feel "rather well," 1.6% "well," and 0.8% "very well" informed about CCU. In de Best-Waldhober et al (2009) respondents were asked about their knowledge of different CCS technologies⁵. The majority of respondents reported

⁵ Six CCS technologies were chosen: 1. Large modern coal fired power stations (for private and commercial use) with CO₂ capture and storage. "IGCC (Integrated Gasification Combined Cycles) with CCS". 2. Conversion of natural gas into electricity (for private and commercial use) with CO₂ capture and storage. "SOFC (Solid Oxide Fuel Cells) with CCS". 3. Large coal fired hydrogen stations (for industrial use and for bus and freight transport) with CO₂ capture

not to have heard of most CCS technologies. Especially enhanced coal bed methane was mostly unfamiliar: 91.4% admitted to be unaware of this technology, and 7.3% stated to know a bit.

- *Drivers of knowledge levels have not been analysed, with a few exceptions.*

Although analyses on the factors behind the social acceptability of CCUS are relatively abundant, this is not the case with the factors driving CCS knowledge levels, which are virtually absent in the literature. One exception, for example, is Perdan et al (2017), who found that gender, education and interest in climate change issues influence CCU knowledge. Men were more likely to know something about CCU than women, the higher-educated respondents were more likely to know about CCU and those respondents more interested in climate change issues had a greater CCU awareness. Schumann (2017) confirms this finding for gender: men more often have a medium or a high level of knowledge about CO₂ transport by pipeline than women, whereas women more often have a low level of knowledge. They also found that age influences CCS awareness: respondents between 35 and 44 years as well as respondents between 45 and 54 years more often had a low level of knowledge about CO₂ pipelines compared to the other age classes. Individuals with no professional qualifications and persons with certified vocational training more often had a low level of knowledge about pipelines, whereas respondents with a degree from a university more often have a medium or a high level of knowledge. In Pietzner et al (2011) respondents with a higher level of education also showed a higher level of CCS awareness. The results in Dowd et al (2014) found that a person's level of understanding of CO₂ characteristics directly impacts his or her understanding of CCS as a technology. Obviously, providing information on CCS can be expected to increase knowledge of the technology. Midden and Huijts (2009) found that 97% and 84% of participants indicated knowing little to nothing about CO₂ storage before and after information was given, respectively.

- *Trends of CCS awareness over time were not analysed and, when they were, an increase in knowledge levels was found.*

Trends regarding the knowledge levels of CCS have been analysed in a few cases. Saito et al (2017) noted that the awareness of CCS had significantly increased in 2015 in Japan compared to 2003 and 2010, however their understanding does not extend to specific details of CCS. As a result, more than 50% of respondents did not state a clear opinion regarding CCS implementation in Japan as a part of their preferred climate policy portfolio. Referring to the Australian case, Steeper (2013) found that awareness of carbon capture and storage as a technology more than doubled from 2006 to 2011 (from 32% to 69%).

4.2 CCUS acceptance

As with CCUS knowledge, comparability of the results of different studies on CCUS acceptability is difficult, because there are different ways to ask the question about it. Some articles ask directly the question on whether CCS is acceptable for respondents (usually on a Likert scale), whereas others compare their acceptability with other mitigation technologies. However, sometimes the question is not asked in terms of acceptability, but in terms of the risk perception of different mitigation technologies (i.e., as in Linzenich et al 2021)⁶ or the impact (positive or negative) that a CCUS project would have on a region (e.g., Brunsting et al 2013) (see the discussion in 2.3 about "perception" versus "acceptance"). There is also an analysis of CCS acceptance following a willingness to pay approach (Amikawa et al 2011)⁷. The following table summarises the results of the articles with respect to the social acceptability of CCS.

and storage. "Hydrogen production via coal gasification with CCS". 4. Conversion of natural gas into hydrogen in large plants (for private and industrial use and bus and freight transport) with CO₂ capture and storage. "Hydrogen production via steam reforming with CCS". 5. Retrieval of methane gas by storing captured CO₂ in coal beds. "ECBM (Enhanced Coal Bed Methane)". 6. Conversion of natural gas into hydrogen (for motor vehicles) with CO₂ capture and storage. "Small scale reforming based on membrane technology with CCS".

⁶ In Linzenich et al (2021), the mean values of the risk perceptions for CCU and the seven renewable and conventional energy technologies were compared. The perceived risk of CCU was at a medium level. CCU ranged between conventional and renewable energy technologies in terms of the risk perception.

⁷ In their analysis on the public acceptance of subsea underground carbon storage in Australia, Japan, Taiwan, Korea, Norway, U.K., U.S., Amikawa et al (2011) found that respondents were willing to pay an additional \$0.74 per month to shift 1% of thermal energy with CCS to renewable energy, i.e., CCS with thermal energy will be preferred to renewable energy if the cost of the former is cheaper than that of the latter by about 0.26 \$/kWh.

Table 5. Results (II). Social acceptability of CCS in the reviewed literature

	Social acceptability of CCS
Itaoka et al. (2005)	<p>Respondents were asked to assess their agreement with a statement of their support for implementing CCS as part of the portfolio, using a 5-point Likert scale. The mean response was 3.4 (i.e., a majority agreed on promoting CCS in implementing a climate policy portfolio). 17.6% were fundamentally opposed to CCS, while 82.4% conditionally supported it.</p> <p>Respondents were more opposed to ocean storage, especially a dilution type of ocean storage. By contrast, they were most likely to favor offshore geological storage.</p>
Shackley et al. (2005)	<p>Most people (48 ± 7%) were neither for nor against CCS or did not know, with a significant number (38 ± 6.5%) expressing slight or strong reservations. Only 13% (±4.5%) volunteered support for the idea.</p> <p>Support for CCS was greater when compared with the main other options (for wind, solar and energy efficiency) than when considered in isolation.</p>
Huijts et al. (2007)	<p>CO₂ storage in general was rated slightly positive on average (avg: 3.17 out of 5.00). Storing CO₂ outside the urban area was judged more positively (avg: 3.50), while attitudes towards storage near the residential area were slightly negative (avg: 2.59).</p>
Tokushige et al. (2007b)	<p>The benefit perception of CO₂ geological storage by the students was higher than the perception of genetically modified food, smoking, global warming, etc. However, it was lower than the perception of renewable energies.</p>
de Best-Waldhober et al. (2009)	<p>12–24% of respondents were very positive about the technology. Only 6% of respondents gave extremely low grades to the CCS options.</p>
Ha-Duong et al. (2009)	<p>The key question about “approval of or opposition to” the use of CCS in France was asked twice, first after presenting the technology, then after explaining its potential adverse consequences. The approval rates were 59% and 38%, respectively. The first time the question was asked, 59% were positive, 48% being rather supportive and 11% strongly supportive. 21% were opposed to the use of CCS in France: 14% rather opposed and 7% strongly opposed.</p> <p>Another question asked participants to select the three most efficient technologies to fight climate warming. CCS remained next to the least efficient technology (selected in their top 3 by only 5% of the respondents).</p>
Itaoka et al. (2009)	<p>People with some knowledge on CCS tended to have a favorable opinion on implementing CCS as part of a larger climate policy portfolio.</p> <p>Regarding the support for the four CCS technologies (ocean- dilution-type, ocean lake-type, geological on-shore, geological offshore-type), the mean results in door-to-door survey were 3.00 to 3.39 out of 5.00 for all technologies. Thus, the public either was neutral or positive about their implementation. By contrast, those polled in the Internet survey had mean results that ranged from 2.88 to 3.73, indicating a large difference in their level of acceptability of the four types of CCS technology: Other than ocean dilution, respondents held positive opinions, with 60% supporting the two geological types of CCS. People with knowledge on CCS in the internet survey often tended to make their choice dependent upon the specific technological type.</p>
Midden and Huijts (2009)	<p>The attitude toward storage nearby was evaluated on average rather negatively (avg = 2.54), on a scale of 1 (undesirable) to 5 (desirable).</p>
Sharp et al. (2009)	<p>Overall, respondents were slightly supportive of CCS development in Canada, rating their support at 4.44 and 4.29 (Canada and Alberta/Saskatchewan sub-samples respectively, results were not statistically different), where 1 indicated strong opposition and 7 indicated strong support.</p>
Duan (2010)	<p>The majority of the Chinese respondents maintained a neutral stance or support about the use of CCS in China (87%), whereas only 12.9% of respondents opposed CCS. 54% of respondents were concerned that the government’s support of CCS would negatively affect investment in other clean energy technologies and renewable energies. 50% of respondents disagreed that CCS was one of the best choices for CO₂ emission reductions in China.</p>

Amikawa et al. (2011)	The marginal willingness to pay was 0.74 \$/percent which means that the respondents were willing to pay an additional \$0.74 per month to shift 1% of thermal energy with CCS to renewable energy, i.e., CCS with thermal energy would be preferred to renewable energy if the cost of the former was cheaper than that of the latter by about 0.26 \$/kWh.
Itaoka et al. (2011)	50% of respondents had a positive opinion on implementing CCS as part of a climate policy portfolio and 42% of respondents had a neutral opinion. However, turning to opinions on implementation of on-shore or off-shore geological storage, more than half of the respondents took a neutral position and positive opinions decreased to 28% for both types of geological storage.
Pietzner et al. (2011)	The initial perceptions in the six countries ranged from a more or less neutral to a slightly positive evaluation regarding the use of CCS technologies, revealed by mean values (from 3.99 out of 7.00 in Germany to 5.03 in Romania). Compared to other energy technologies, the use of CCS technologies was evaluated much less positively, only nuclear energy received lower rankings. To address global warming, renewable energy technologies and energy efficiency technologies were the responses most frequently given by respondents.
de Best-Waldhober et al. (2012)	The two CCS options, "Large plants where coal or gas are converted into electricity with CCS" and "Large plants where gas is converted into hydrogen with CCS" were evaluated negatively by most respondents (5.34 and 5.92 out of 10 , respectively). Most other options were assessed positively on average (energy efficiency: 7.33, wind: 7.15; biomass: 7.41, nuclear: 5.29). Respondents were asked to choose three out of the seven options to solve the policy problem. Most respondents choose either energy efficiency (90.2%), wind energy (75.4%) or biomass (70%). The two CCS options were chosen by a small percentage of respondents as one of their three preferred options (6.9% and 10.6% , respectively). The first CCS option ("Large plants where coal or gas is converted to electricity with CCS") was rejected by 11.0% of respondents. The second CCS option ("Large plants where natural gas is converted to hydrogen with CCS") was rejected by 6.8% of respondents.
Kraeusel and Möst (2012)	The attitude towards CCS was neutral . Moreover, acceptance of CCS was an important factor for the willingness to pay. The level of willingness to pay for CCS technology was much lower than for renewable energy.
Moutenet et al. (2012)	In 2010, respondents did not generally reject CCS technology or a potential pilot project in their region. In fact, they were slightly favorable toward such a project. In 2011, the picture changed slightly, given the intense debate on shale gas exploration in the province at the end of 2010. Respondents were less likely to be favorable toward the use of CCS. 54% of the respondents in 2011 (62% in 2010) said they were favorable toward the use of CCS in the province. In addition, 45% of the respondents in 2011 (55% in 2010) said they also support the implementation of a pilot project in their region. Concerning the Bécancour/Trois-Rivières (B/TR) region, after presenting the two opposing NGO opinions, 32% of the respondents in 2011 (40% in 2010) were favorable to the use of CCS. In addition, 30% in 2011 (41% in 2010) were also favorable to the implementation of a CCS pilot project in this region. In 2010, respondents did not generally reject CCS technology or a potential pilot project in their region. 39% of Québécois supported the implementation of a pilot project in their region.
Terwel et al. (2012)	When asked how good or bad they thought the CCS plan was, over two-thirds of the respondents (69%) indicated to find the plan "very bad" and 16% of the respondents found it "quite bad".
Wallquist et al. (2012)	Scenarios that do not involve a pipeline near participants' homes were generally more accepted than the ones involving CO ₂ or gas pipelines. For plants, scenarios with biogas-fueled plants were higher ranked than those with conventional gas. For different storage locations, a clear picture of acceptance preferences did not emerge.

Brunsting et al. (2013)	Of the Polish respondents who have heard of CCS, 61% thought that a CCS project would have a slight to very positive impact on the region and 20% thought that a CCS project would have a slight to very negative impact on the region. The remaining 19% either did not expect positive or negative impacts or did not know.
Steeper (2013)	Despite the low level of awareness, once respondents were told about plans for the project in their region 59% were comfortable with the plans, 24% were uncomfortable and 17% were undecided. 53% of respondents were concerned about geosequestration generally, with community and environmental safety and potential leakage of CO ₂ being the main concerns. The number of respondents who claimed they were comfortable with the presence of the Otway Project in their region increased from 33% in 2006 to 48% in 2011, with a further 19% being neutral. Those in local communities were also more likely to be comfortable (52% vs. 43% Warrnambool).
Dütschke et al. (2014)	The overall mean across the 18 settings is 4.3 which corresponds to a neutral perception towards the CCS settings described on average (possible values of the scale reached from 1 to 7, with higher numbers referring to more positive ratings). The range of the setting ratings varied from 3.8 to 4.7 , thus from neutral to slightly positive. Those two settings which were rated worst both included a coal-fired power plant as CO ₂ source and saline aquifers as storage option. The two receiving the best ratings included biomass as the CO ₂ source and did not mention a pipeline. No such clear effects were observed for the two further steps in the CCS chain transport and storage. Perceptions for these two factors were dependent on each other in case of storage in a depleted natural gas field. Thus, the reference to a pipeline did not have an overall negative effect in their study. Storage in a saline aquifer was perceived more negatively than storage in combination with EGR.
Kaiser et al. (2014)	55% of the respondents had positive expectations of what CCS might bring to the area and only 18% thought that a CCS project would have a negative impact on the region. On balance, a majority of respondents said that they supported CCS both locally and nationally.
Krause et al. (2014)	80% of respondents supported the general use of CCS. However, 20% of these initial supporters exhibited a NIMBY (Non-In-My-Back-Yard)-like reaction and switched to opposition as a CCS facility was proposed close to their communities.
Li et al. (2014)	From the respondents' perspectives, nuclear power and CCUS compared largely unfavourably with renewables and energy efficiency in order to mitigate climate change (however, no precise data were provided). Moreover, a large proportion of respondents were concerned about the risks of CCUS. The NIMBY phenomenon focused mainly on two processes (transportation and storage)(again, specific data were not provided).
Schumann et al. (2014)	The majority of the German public would prefer CO ₂ to be stored nowhere at all (31.4% of all respondents). The rejection of CO ₂ storage in general which is reflected in the answer "nowhere" was visibly higher in North Frisia (38%) than in the rest of Germany or in Aurich plus islands. Nationwide, the general rejection of CO ₂ storage was higher than in Aurich plus islands (25%). Nationwide, CO ₂ transport via pipeline was generally assessed neutrally and offshore storage would be preferred, while respondents from the coastal regions would prefer onshore storage near the emission source. CO ₂ onshore storage was evaluated more negatively than CO ₂ offshore storage in the nationwide survey.
Warren et al. (2014)	30.1% in the sample strongly supported a CCS facility in Indiana. When those who somewhat supported such a facility were added, 75.5% of the sample supported CCS. A minority of respondents (22.1%) strongly or somewhat opposed an in-state CCS facility, with 10.6% in strong opposition.
Chen et al. (2015)	Except for nuclear and CCS, all other carbon-free energy technologies enjoy widespread public support (over 70% support rate). CCS: 57% support (with 36% strongly supportive), 38% does not have an opinion and 5% opposes it.

Dütschke et al. (2016)	The participants preferred the use of renewable energy sources to CCS. The two scenarios with the most positive average ratings had a biomass power plant as the capture facility and did not pay reference to a pipeline in the transport step (both with a rating of 4.7 in average). The two scenarios which received the most negative average rating both present coal as CO ₂ source and storage into saline aquifers (3.8 and 3.9). Regarding the CO ₂ source, coal (avg = 4.1) was rated significantly less positively than biomass (avg = 4.5) or industry. If storage in a depleted natural gas field was explicitly combined with a pipeline for transport, the scenario rating was significantly less positive than for the scenario which did not refer to a pipeline in a 1-7 likert scale.
Yang et al. (2016)	51% of respondents in the Chinese representative survey were not likely to support CCS application of CCS technologies as an alternative technological option to mitigate climate change.
Boyd et al. (2017)	61% opposed or strongly opposed a CCS project being constructed within 25 km of their home. Only 8.9% supported or strongly supported it.
Perdan et al. (2017)	51% were in favour of CCU while only 2% of respondents indicated opposition to CCU. 23% of respondents were indifferent ("neither in favour nor opposed" responses) and 17% "didn't know". The respondents were asked to indicate whether they would be worried about possible location of a CCU plant within their community. 52% of these indicated that they would not be worried while 22% said they would be worried. 26% of the respondents said that they did not know whether they would be worried or not.
Schumann (2017)	The personal and societal risk of CO ₂ transport by pipeline was assessed neutrally on average. However, a comparison of the means indicated that the societal risk of a CO ₂ pipeline was assessed higher than the personal risk. The respondents' general attitude towards a CO ₂ pipeline was on average neutral. On average, the willingness to actively protest against a CO ₂ pipeline close to one's own home was slightly above the neutral assessment.
Offerman-van Heek et al. (2018)	The participants were generally positive about CCU products (indicated by a significantly higher mean than the mid-point scale). Among the given CCU product options, CCU fuels were perceived as the best option for the utilization of CO ₂ , while CCU mattresses and CO ₂ usage for the carbonization of beverages were both evaluated significantly less positively in comparison to CCU fuels.
Arning et al. (2019)	CCS and CCU were positively perceived, but CCU reached significantly higher acceptance ratings (average CCS = 4.85 out of 7.00, average CCU = 5.63), a more positive benefit perception (avg CCS = 3.6, avg CCU= 3.88), and lower barrier perceptions (avg CCS = 3.9, avg CCU = 3.72) than CCS. However, local acceptance decreased when either a CCS- or a CCU-site was supposed to be developed in the closer area and even turned to a slight (CCU) or even stronger (CCS) rejection.
Ashworth et al. (2019)	Participants were asked to rank the energy sources/technologies in the priority order that they would allocate public funds for their development and implementation (where 1 = most funding support to 12 = lowest funding support). CCS ranked 8 out of the 12 in Australia and 10 out of 12 in China.
Linzenich et al. (2019)	While acceptance of CCU was rather neutral (avg CCU = 5.63), CCS was rated significantly lower and slightly negatively (an average of 4.81 in a 1 to 10 scale).
Saito et al. (2019)	54.4% of respondents did not have an opinion towards CCS as part of a climate policy portfolio. 36.1% of the respondents answered that they would support it, and 9.5% answered that they were against it. When it came to implementing more concrete offshore CCS plans (the plans were explained as hypothetical in the questionnaire), negative opinions increased. Nevertheless, 54.4% of all respondents did not have any opinion on the implementation of CCS. In terms of proximity of the CCS site, less people opposed implementing "CCS offshore at tens of kilometers off the coast near Japan" than "CCS offshore at a few kilometers away from the closest shore to their house".
Whitmarsh et al. (2019)	Despite more awareness in Norway, the greatest support for CCS was in the UK. The lowest support occurred in the Netherlands. Local samples (i.e., close to current or

	potential CCS sites) were more supportive of CCS being implemented than national samples (especially in the UK).
Wolske et al. (2019)	Support for bioenergy with carbon capture and storage (BECCS) and direct air capture (DAC) was lower than support for afforestation and reforestation (AR).
Cox et al. (2020)	BECCs was preferred over direct air capture (DAC).
Sun et al. (2020)	The public's explicit attitudes towards CCS were positive, since the rate of perceived value was higher than the rate of perceived general risk and perceived performance risk. The explicit attitudes of the public were more favorable towards CCS than their implicit attitudes. The public were indifferent towards CCS and nuclear projects.
Broecks et al. (2021)	Citizens in the Netherlands and the UK were, on average, neutral to slightly positive about the implementation of industrial CCS in their country after they had read information about CO ₂ , climate change, industrial CCS and its outcomes.
Ferguson and Ashworth (2021)	Support for CCS: 3.85 (likert scale: 1 to 7), which was lower than solar, wind, hydro, wave and geothermal. There was a higher support for CCS compared to biomass, coal, nuclear and coal seam gas. Respondents were also asked to rank the twelve energy technologies in the priority order they would allocate public funds towards their development and implementation. Renewable energies consistently ranked in the top five positions (solar (PV), solar (thermal), hydroelectric, wind and wave). Geothermal appeared in the sixth position and CCS appeared in the eighth position.
Lima et al. (2021)	Most of the public supported the development of CCS in Brazil (83% in Sao ~ Mateus and 81% in Vitoria).
Linzenich et al. (2021)	The mean values of the risk perceptions for CCU and the seven renewable and conventional energy technologies were compared. The perceived risk of CCU was at a medium level. CCU ranged between conventional and renewable energy technologies in terms of the risk perception.
Koukouzas et al. (2022)	35% of respondents agreed with the development of CCS in their country. 70% believed that the adoption of CCS in Europe was not acceptable.
Merk et al. (2022)	Respondents from both countries (Norway and Germany) did not evaluate offshore and onshore storage differently. Norwegian respondents evaluated a project where foreign sourced CO ₂ was stored in Norway substantially more negatively compared to a project where domestically sourced CO ₂ was stored in Norway. By contrast, German respondents were not affected by the variation of the nationality of emissions or the storage site.

Source: Own elaboration. Note: Only those articles which report data on acceptance are included.

- *The acceptability of CCS is neutral to slightly positive.*

Although, as mentioned above, it is difficult to compare the results from different studies and provide an aggregated picture, given the different methodologies and the different manners in which the acceptability question is asked, the results in the previous table suggest that most people are neutral to slightly positive about the implementation of CCS in their country.

- *Considerable differences across countries exist.*

As with CCUS awareness, the acceptability of CCUS is likely to differ across national settings. This is clearly the case in the article by Pietzner et al (2011), which shows that the initial perceptions in the six countries they analyse range from a more or less neutral to a slightly positive evaluation regarding the use of CCS technologies, revealed by mean values (3.99 out of 7.00 in Germany to 5.03 in Romania). Whereas Greece and Romania would, on average, slightly support the use of CCS technologies to address global warming, Germany, the Netherlands, Norway and the United Kingdom were on average essentially neutral regarding the use of CCS. The cross-country comparison in Whitmarsh et al (2019) also revealed that, despite more awareness in Norway, the greatest support for CCS occurred in the UK, whereas the lowest support was found in the Netherlands.

There might also be differences within regions in countries. For example, Schumann et al (2014) found that the majority of the German public would spontaneously prefer CO₂ to be stored nowhere at all (31.4% of all respondents) but the rejection to CO₂ storage was higher in North Frisia (38%) than in the rest of Germany or in Aurich plus islands.

- *There is strong evidence of NIMBY and NUMBY*

Evidence on the existence of a Not-In-My-Back-Yard (NIMBY) or Not-Under-My-Back-Yard (NUMBY) phenomena could be found. For example, in Krause et al (2014), over 80% of respondents expressed support for the general use of CCS technology, but 20% of these initial supporters exhibited a NIMBY-like reaction and switched to opposition as a CCS facility was proposed close to their communities. In their study on Canada, Boyd et al (2017) found that 61% opposed or strongly opposed a CCS project being constructed within 25 km of their home, whereas only 8.9% support or strongly supported it. Li et al (2014) showed that the NIMBY phenomenon was focused mainly on two processes: transportation and storage. In Arning et al (2019), local acceptance decreased when either a CCS or a CCU site was supposed to be developed in the closer area and even turned to a slight (CCU) or even stronger (CCS) rejection. In Wallquist et al (2012), scenarios that did not involve a pipeline near participants' homes were generally more accepted than the ones involving CO₂ or gas pipelines. In Saito et al (2019), less people opposed implementing "CCS offshore at tens of kilometers off the coast near Japan" than "CCS offshore at a few kilometers away from the closest shore to their house". In Huijts et al (2007), CO₂ storage in general was rated slightly positive on average (avg: 3.17 out of 5.00), storing CO₂ outside the urban area was judged more positively (avg: 3.50), while attitudes towards storage near the residential area were slightly negative (avg: 2.59).

However, somehow surprisingly, a few articles report evidence of NIMBY not being problematic (or even people being in favour of the location of a CCS project nearby). For example, in Perdan et al (2017), more than a half of the respondents (52%) indicated that they would not be worried about possible location of a CCU plant within their community, while 22% said they would be worried⁸. 30.1% of the sample in Warren et al (2014) strongly supported a CCS facility in Indiana. When those who somewhat supported such a facility were added, 75.5% of the sample indicated support for CCS. A minority of respondents (22.1%) strongly or somewhat opposed an in-state CCS facility, with 10.6% in strong opposition. In Whitmarsh et al (2019), local samples (i.e., close to current or potential CCS sites) were more supportive of CCS being implemented than national samples.

- *CCS is generally less preferred than other mitigation options.*

Compared to other mitigation options, the studies show that CCS is less preferred. For example, Li et al (2014) found that nuclear power and CCS compared largely unfavourably with other climate mitigation options (such as wind power, solar power, energy efficiency, or biomass). In Ashworth et al (2019), participants were asked to rank the energy sources/technologies in the priority order that they would allocate public funds for their development and implementation (where 1 = most funding support to 12 = lowest funding support). CCS ranked 8 out of the 12 in Australia and 10 out of 12 in China. The participants preferred the use of renewable energy sources to CCS in Dütschke et al (2016). In de Best-Waldhober et al (2012), the two CCS options were evaluated somewhat negatively by most respondents (5.34 and 5.92 out of 10.00), whereas most of the other options were assessed positively on average (energy efficiency: 7.33, wind: 7.15; biomass: 7.41, nuclear: 5.29). Chen et al (2015) found that support for CCS was much lower (57%) than for other carbon-free technologies (above 70%): 57% supported CCS (with 36% being strongly supportive), 38% did not have an opinion and 5% opposed it. Support for CCS was also lower in Ferguson and Ashworth (2021), at 3.85 (likert scale: 1 to 7), compared to solar, wind, hydro, wave and geothermal. However, CCS was more supported than biomass, coal, nuclear and coal seam gas. When the respondents were asked to rank the twelve energy technologies in the priority order they would allocate public funds towards their development and implementation, renewable energies ranked in the top five positions, whereas CCS appeared in the eighth position.

Some studies find evidence that CCS is more supported when considered in combination with other technologies. In Shackley et al (2005), support for CCS was somewhat greater when combined with the main other options (for wind, solar and energy efficiency) than when considered in isolation. In their study on Canada, Sharp et al (2009) showed that respondents held a belief that CCS was less risky than normal oil and gas industry operations, nuclear power, or

⁸ 26% of respondents said that they did not know whether they would be worried or not.

coal-burning power plants. There was support for the use of CCS in combination with energy efficiency and alternative energy technologies in order to retain public support.

- *Analyses of the time trend of acceptability of CCS have been virtually missing.*

It could be assumed that the perception and acceptability of CCS would change overtime, according to the evolution of the costs and maturity of the technology itself as well as the socioeconomic, institutional and environmental context (more relevance attached to climate change mitigation, to the dependence on foreign energy sources etc...). However, somehow surprisingly, there isn't an analysis of CCS acceptability overtime. One exception is Steeper 2013, who finds that the number of respondents who claimed they were comfortable with the presence of the Otway Project in their region increased from 33% in 2006 to 48% in 2011, with a further 19% neutral.

- *There are significant differences across CCUS alternatives:*

Within CCUS, some differences in the acceptability can be observed across stages or components.

CCU vs. CCS. CO₂ transport via pipeline.

In Arning et al (2019), CCU reached significantly higher acceptance ratings, a more positive benefit perception and lower barrier perceptions than CCS. In Dütschke et al (2016), if storage in a depleted natural gas field is explicitly combined with a pipeline for transport, the scenario rating is significantly less positive than for the scenario which does not make reference to a pipeline. In contrast, in Schumann et al (2014), nationwide, CO₂ transport via pipeline was generally assessed neutrally.

Acceptability of different options for CCU.

Offerman-van Heek et al (2018) show that, although respondents had a positive view of CCU products, CCU fuels were perceived as the best option for the utilization of CO₂ among the CCU product options, while CCU mattresses and CO₂ usage for the carbonization of beverages were both evaluated significantly less positively in comparison to CCU fuels.

On-shore vs. off-shore storage.

The existing evidence shows contradictory results regarding a preference of off-shore storage versus on-shore storage, with evidence in favour, against and neutral regarding one choice versus the other. Schumann et al (2014) found that, nationwide, offshore storage would be preferred over onshore one, while respondents from the coastal regions would prefer onshore storage near the emission source, but no statistical differences could be found in the general attitudes towards the two storage options in the regional surveys. In Itaoka et al (2009), respondents held positive opinions about the support for the four CCS technologies (ocean- dilution-type, ocean lake-type, geological on-shore, geological offshore-type), except for ocean dilution. Similarly, in Itaoka et al (2005), respondents were more opposed to a dilution type of ocean storage, but they were most likely to favor offshore geological storage. However, in Itaoka et al (2011), more than half of the respondents took a neutral position regarding the implementation of on-shore versus off-shore geological storage. Similarly, in Merk et al (2022), respondents from both countries (Norway and Germany) did not evaluate offshore and onshore storage differently.

Source of CO₂: coal-fired power plants rated less positively than both biomass or industry.

There is very tiny evidence on the acceptability of the source of CO₂. To the best of our knowledge, only Dütschke et al (2016) has shown that coal is rated significantly less positively than biomass or industry.

BECCs vs. DAC.

Regarding the type of CO₂ removal, a couple of papers focus on the acceptability of two alternatives: biomass energy with carbon capture and storage (BECCs) and Direct Air Capture (DAC). BECCs is preferred over DAC in Cox et al (2020), whereas Wolske et al (2019) do not show differences in the acceptability between both options⁹.

⁹ These authors found that support for BECCS and DAC was lower than support for afforestation and reforestation, as BECCS and DAC were perceived to tamper with nature more.

Foreign sourced vs. domestically sourced CO₂.

An interesting paper in this regard is Merk et al (2022). In their analysis of Norway and Germany, they found that “Norwegian respondents evaluate a project where foreign sourced CO₂ is stored in Norway substantially more negatively compared to a project where domestically sourced CO₂ is stored in Norway. By contrast, German respondents are not affected by the variation of the nationality of emissions or the storage site” (Merk et al 2022, p.1).

4.3 Drivers and barriers of CCUS acceptance.

The reviewed articles provide interesting insights on the analysis of the drivers and barriers to the acceptability of CCUS. An inductive approach was followed to extract the specific factors enhancing or inhibiting the acceptability of CCUS. These very specific factors were then grouped, leading to 9 broad categories (4.3.1). Then, an analysis of the direction of the impact of specific factor was carried out across different articles, identifying such direction for each article and inferring conclusions for the broad category. In addition, the level of evidence on the specific factor as well as the level of agreement between different articles on the direction of the specific factor are reported. Although it is rather obvious that drivers and barriers are two sides of the same coin, a focused analysis is performed, first, for drivers (4.3.2), and then for barriers (4.3.3). We also analyse in 4.3.4 which specific factors are not relevant, in the sense that either a statistically significant relationship between the factor and CCUS acceptability can not be inferred (when inferential methods are used) or that the factor is not considered important (when a descriptive statistics approach is adopted). This subsection closes with a qualitative synthesis of the results (4.3.5).

4.3.1 Broad and specific categories.

The factors considered in this report are inferred from the literature review. Based on the specific items identified in the literature, broad categories are built which each includes subsets of those items. Those **broad categories** include:

- Sociodemographics
- Proximity, place of residence and local acceptability
- Benefit and risk perception
- Political ideology, worldview, CC awareness, environmental awareness
- Knowledge of CCUS
- Contribution to mitigation
- Perception of technoeconomic features of CCUS: costs, maturity
- Environmental and security of supply benefits
- Trust
- Information provision
- Economic impacts
- Different technologies/applications
- Other (miscellaneous)

The following subsections provides details on the different items which are included in each broad category.

4.3.2 Drivers/enablers.

In this section the results for the drivers are reported. Tables per broad category are provided. Each of these tables include information on the number of articles which identify either a positive (+) or a negative (-) relationship between the specific factor and CCUS acceptability. In addition, a conclusion per item regarding the net impact of the factor on CCUS acceptability, the level of evidence and the level of agreement between the different articles is provided.

Regarding the level of evidence, this has been classified using the following scale: VL=Very Low; L=Low; M=Medium; H=High; VH=Very high. For the level of agreement, we count the articles which show a positive (+) or a negative (-) relation between the specific factor and CCUS acceptability and identify the level of agreement using the same 5-point Likert scale according to table 6. The result for the level of evidence of the item is only reported when there are more than 1 article for the item. However, those items with <2 articles are mentioned. The level of agreement is mentioned only when there are more than 4 articles in the item.

Table 6. Number of articles to include a given item in the scales of the "level of evidence" and "level of agreement".

Scale	Level of evidence	Level of agreement
Very low (VL)	< 4	Same (+) answers and (-) answers
Low (L)	≥ 4	Only one more (+) answer than a (-) one
Medium (M)	≥ 7	Two more (+) answers than (-) ones
High (H)	≥ 9	Three or four more (+) answers than (-) answers
Very High (H)	≥ 12	More than five (+) answers than (-) answers

Section 4.3.2.1. will provide the results of the analysis for the drivers per item and broad category, whereas section 4.3.2.2 will summarise the results.

4.3.2.1 Drivers per broad category and item.

SOCIODEMOGRAPHICS:

	Age	Gender (male)	Income	Education
(+)	4	6	4	4
(-)	2	3	0	0
Conclusion (item)	More age, more acceptance	Males tend to accept more than females	More income, more acceptance	More education, more acceptance
Level of evidence	L	H	L	L
Level of agreement	L	H	H	H

Level of evidence/level of agreement: VL=very low; L=Low; M=medium; H=High; VH=Very high. Other items with <2 articles: nationality.

General conclusion on the category: Socio-demographic variables have a limited explanatory power of CCS acceptance.

- **PROXIMITY, PLACE OF RESIDENCE, LOCAL ACCEPTABILITY.**

In this case, all the items have a very low level of evidence (<1 article): living in urban areas, living in the North of France, living in the prairie, proximity and proximity to coal fired power plant. The few existing articles provide the following insights: Those living in urban areas and the North of France and in the prairie provinces of Canada have more acceptance for CCS and when the respondents live closer to a CCS site (potential or current), they show more support to CCS (i.e., proximity to a coal plant increases the acceptance of CCS). However, given the very small level

of evidence, the **general conclusion on the category** is that the place of residence and proximity to the CCS or coal plant do not seem to have an impact on CCS acceptance.

- **BENEFIT PERCEPTION**

	Benefit perception
(+)	19
(-)	0
Conclusion (item)	The greater the perception of benefits of the CCUS plant, the greater the level of acceptance.
Level of evidence	VH
Level of agreement	VH

Level of evidence/level of agreement: VL=very low; L=Low; M=medium; H=High; VH=Very high. Other items with <2 articles: none.

General conclusion on the category: Benefit perception of CCUS plays a relevant role in explaining CCUS acceptance.

- **IDEOLOGY, WORLDVIEW, CLIMATE CHANGE (CC) AWARENESS, ENVIRONMENTAL AWARENESS**

	CC awareness	Political ideology	Self-efficacy	Positive emotion/affect*
(+)	12	2	2	4
(-)	0	0	0	0
Conclusion (item)	CC awareness is a good predictor of CCUS acceptance	Those with a political ideology on the right have a greater acceptance of CCUS	The greater the level of self-efficacy, the greater the acceptability of CCUS	The greater the level of positive emotion/affect, the greater the acceptability of CCUS
Level of evidence	H	VL	VL	L
Level of agreement	VH	-	-	VH

Level of evidence/level of agreement: VL=very low; L=Low; M=medium; H=High; VH=Very high. Other items with <2 articles: environmental awareness, egalitarian worldview. * This refers to individual's emotional response to the technology, such as worry or hope (as in Moon 2020). For example, in order to understand the role of emotions in CCS, Moon (2020) proposes the hypothesis that positive CCS affect will relate positively to (a) individual-level CCS support and (b) perceived community-level CCS support.

General conclusion on the category: Awareness of the climate change problem leads to greater CCUS support. Other aspects related to ideology and worldviews have not been found to play an important role (underresearched).

- **KNOWLEDGE OF CCUS**

	Knowledge of CCUS
(+)	11
(-)	1
Conclusion (item)	The greater the level of previous knowledge of CCUS, the greater the level of CCUS acceptance
Level of evidence	H
Level of agreement	VH

Level of evidence/level of agreement: VL=very low; L=Low; M=medium; H=High; VH=Very high. The level of agreement is mentioned only when there are more than 4 articles in the item. Other items with <2 articles: none.

General conclusion on the category: The greater the level of previous knowledge/awareness of CCUS, the greater the level of CCUS acceptance.

- **CONTRIBUTION TO CLIMATE CHANGE MITIGATION**

	Climate change (CC) mitigation
(+)	15
(-)	0
Conclusion (item)	CCUS is believed to contribute to CC mitigation, which increases its acceptance.
Level of evidence	VH
Level of agreement	VH

Level of evidence/level of agreement: VL=very low; L=Low; M=medium; H=High; VH=Very high. Other items with <2 articles: Bridging technology.

General conclusion on the category: The contribution of CCUS to climate change mitigation is related to its acceptance.

- **PERCEPTION OF TECHNOECONOMIC FEATURES OF CCUS: COSTS, MATURITY**

	Cost of CCUS	CCUS is mature and sustainable	The perceived innovativeness of CCUS is a driver of CCUS acceptance
(+)	2	2	2
(-)	0	0	0
Conclusion (item)	The lower the costs of CCUS or the lower the costs of CCUS with respect to other mitigation technologies, the greater CCUS acceptance	The more mature CCUS is believed to be, the greater the level of CCUS acceptance	The perceived innovativeness of CCUS is a factor which enhances CCUS acceptance
Level of evidence	VL	VL	VL
Level of agreement	-	-	-

Level of evidence/level of agreement: VL=very low; L=Low; M=medium; H=High; VH=Very high. Other items with <2 articles: CCUS requires fewer style changes.

General conclusion on the category: Several aspects of the perception of the technoeconomic features of CCUS are positively related to its acceptance, but the evidence is very low. This is clearly an underresearched area.

- **ENVIRONMENTAL AND SECURITY OF SUPPLY BENEFITS**

	Environmental benefits	It reduces fossil fuel (FF) dependence
(+)	8	4
(-)	0	0
Conclusion (item)	The "env benefits" is a factor which enhances CCS acceptance	The reduction of FF dependence is a factor positively influencing its acceptance
Level of evidence	M	L
Level of agreement	VH	VH

Level of evidence/level of agreement: VL=very low; L=Low; M=medium; H=High; VH=Very high. Other items with <2 articles: Smog reduction, acid rain, better air quality, noise, resource depletion, water pollution, reliability of energy supply, more sustainable production.

General conclusion on the category: The environmental benefits of CCUS are related to acceptance.

- **TRUST**

	Trust	Trust on the government	Trust on the industry
(+)	4	5	3
(-)	0	0	0
Conclusion (item)	Trust	Those who trust the government	Trust on the industry
Level of evidence	L	L	VL
Level of agreement	VH	VH	

Level of evidence/level of agreement: VL=very low; L=Low; M=medium; H=High; VH=Very high. Other items with <2 articles: National or provincial local entity that manages CCUS is preferred over industry managing CCUS, local government preferred over national government, trust in NGOs trust in scientists and public trust.

General conclusion on the category: Trust in different actors is positively related to CCUS acceptance, but to a limited extent.

- **INFORMATION PROVISION**

	Information provision	Trust in information	Social normative information
(+)	10	2	2
(-)	1	0	0
Conclusion (item)	Providing information on CCUS increases its acceptability	Trust in information	Social normative information
Level of evidence	H	VL	VL
Level of agreement	VH		

Level of evidence/level of agreement: VL=very low; L=Low; M=medium; H=High; VH=Very high. Other items with <2 articles: none.

General conclusion on the category: The acceptability of CCUS is positively related to information provision.

- **ECONOMIC IMPACTS**

In this broad category, the three items (employment effects, effects on industrial companies and priority on economic development) had only one article per item. The results show that each item has a positive effect on acceptance. Therefore, the **general conclusion on the category is that** the economic impacts of CCUS on acceptance tend to be positive, but given the small evidence, we can not really infer a relevant influence on its acceptability. This is clearly an underresearched field.

4.3.2.2 Summary of drivers.

The main findings on the impact of drivers on CCUS acceptability can be summarized as follows regarding the broad categories of drivers:

- Socio-demographic variables have a limited explanatory power of CCUS acceptance.
- Place of residence and proximity to the CCS or coal plant do not seem to have an impact on CCS acceptance.
- Benefit perception of CCUS plays a relevant role in explaining CCUS acceptance
- Awareness of the climate change problem leads to greater CCUS support. Other aspects related to ideology and worldviews have not been found to play an important role (underresearched).
- Previous knowledge of CCUS is clearly related in a positive manner with CCUS support.
- The contribution of CCUS to climate change mitigation is related to its acceptance.
- Several aspects of the perception of the technoeconomic features of CCUS are positively related to its acceptance, although this is clearly an underresearched area.
- The environmental benefits of CCUS are related to acceptance.
- Trust in different actors is positively related to CCUS acceptance, but to a limited extent.
- The acceptability of CCUS is positively related to information provision.
- The economic impacts of CCUS do not have a relevant influence on its acceptability.
- Different applications and CCUS stages have different degree of acceptability.

4.3.3 Barriers

A similar type of analysis as with the drivers is carried out for the barriers. Section 4.3.3.1. provides the results of the analysis for the drivers per item and broad category, whereas section 4.3.1.2 summarises the results.

4.3.3.1 Barriers per broad category and item.

In this section the results for the barriers are reported. Tables per broad category are provided. Each of these tables include information on the number of articles which identify either a negative (-) or a positive (+) relationship between the specific factor and CCUS acceptability. A (-) relationship means that the item is a barrier to CCUS acceptability, whereas a (+) relationship means that the item is a driver of CCUS acceptability.

- **SOCIODEMOGRAPHICS**

	Gender (male)	Age	Income	Education	Respondents with children
(-)	6	2	2	1	2
(+)	2	0	2	3	0
Conclusion (item)	Women are more against CCUS than men	Increasing age, less support for CCUS	A higher or a lower income level is not related to CCUS support.	A lower level of education generally leads to a lower support for CCUS	Having children (and the number of children) is negatively related to CCUS support
Level of evidence	M	VL	L	L	VL
Level of agreement	H		VL	M	

Level of evidence/level of agreement: VL=very low; L=Low; M=medium; H=High; VH=Very high. Other items with <2 articles: Employment.

General conclusion on the category: Sociodemographic features of the respondents have a limited and sometimes ambiguous relation with CCUS acceptance, except in the case of gender (with women generally more opposed).

- **PROXIMITY, PLACE OF RESIDENCE AND LOCAL ACCEPTABILITY**

	Proximity
(-)	12
(+)	0
Conclusion (item)	A greater proximity to the CCUS project reduces the acceptability of CCUS.
Level of evidence	VH
Level of agreement	VH

Level of evidence/level of agreement: VL=very low; L=Low; M=medium; H=High; VH=Very high. Other variables with <2 articles: Living in a coal mining region, Living in underprivileged neighbourhoods (=income), Living in a tourism region.

General conclusion on the category: Proximity to the CCUS project has a clearly negative impact on CCUS acceptance. Other aspects of the place of residence of respondents seem to play a limited role in this regard.

- **RISK/SAFETY PERCEPTION**

	Risks	Safety concerns
(-)	20	4
(+)	1	0
Conclusion (item)	The greatest the perception of the risks of CCUS, the lower CCUS acceptability	Safety concerns
Level of evidence	VH	L
Level of agreement	VH	VH

Level of evidence/level of agreement: VL=very low; L=Low; M=medium; H=High; VH=Very high. Other items with <2 articles: disposal risks, CO₂ product risks.

General conclusion: The results show that, clearly, perception of the risks of CCUS negatively affects its acceptance.

- **IDEOLOGY, WORLDVIEW, CLIMATE CHANGE AWARENESS, ENVIRONMENTAL AWARENESS**

	Climate change (CC) awareness
(-)	3
(+)	2
Conclusion (item)	Ambiguous effects of CC awareness. For 3 studies the more aware of CC the respondents are, the lower the acceptability of CCS. For 2 studies, the less aware of CC (skeptics), the lower the level of CCS acceptability.
Level of evidence	L
Level of agreement	L

Level of evidence/level of agreement: VL=very low; L=Low; M=medium; H=High; VH=Very high. Other items with <2 articles: environmental awareness, political ideology.

General conclusion: The opinions on whether a higher awareness of the CC challenge entails a greater CCUS support are mixed. Other aspects of ideology and worldviews have not played an important role in the literature (underresearched).

- **CCUS KNOWLEDGE**

	Knowledge of CCUS
(-)	3
(+)	0
Conclusion (item)	The greater the level of previous knowledge of CCS, the lower the acceptability of CCUS.
Level of evidence	VL
Level of agreement	

Level of evidence/level of agreement: VL=very low; L=Low; M=medium; H=High; VH=Very high. Other items with <2 articles: none.

General conclusion: The greater the level of previous knowledge of CCUS, the lower the acceptability of CCUS.

- **CONTRIBUTION TO CLIMATE CHANGE MITIGATION**

	Mitigation deterrence	Climate change mitigation
(-)	5	2
(+)	0	0
Conclusion (item)	CCUS is argued to deter investments in other mitigation technologies and, thus, to deter mitigation.	CCUS is not regarded as a solution to CC mitigation.
Level of evidence	L	VL
Level of agreement	VH	

Level of evidence/level of agreement: VL=very low; L=Low; M=medium; H=High; VH=Very high. Other items with <2 articles: none.

General conclusion: Respondents are highly critical with the role that CCUS can play in mitigation. There seems to be a concern that CCUS will deter investments in other mitigation technologies and, thus, to deter mitigation.

- **PERCEPTION OF TECHNOECONOMIC FEATURES OF CCUS: COSTS AND MATURITY.**

	Mentioning modest costs of CCUS deployment	Immaturity of CCUS
(-)	3	2
(+)	0	0
Conclusion (item)	The greater the costs of CCUS, the lower its acceptability	The lower maturity of CCUS compared to other energy technologies is argued to be a barrier to its acceptance, but only by a very limited number of studies
Level of evidence	VL	VL
Level of agreement		

Level of evidence/level of agreement: VL=very low; L=Low; M=medium; H=High; VH=Very high. Other items with <2 articles: none.

General conclusion: The acceptability of CCUS seems to be negatively related to the costs of CCUS and to its lower maturity compared to other mitigation technologies.

- **ENVIRONMENTAL AND SECURITY OF SUPPLY BENEFITS**

	Groundwater pollution	Leakage	Health environmental risks	Effect on environment
(-)	2	9	2	5
(+)	1	0	0	0
Conclusion (item)	Groundwater pollution	leakage	Health env risks	Effect on env
Level of evidence	VL	H	VL	L
Level of agreement		VH		VH

Level of evidence/level of agreement: VL=very low; L=Low; M=medium; H=High; VH=Very high. Other items with <2 articles: Rejecting injecting CO₂ underground, harm to plants and animals, sustainability concerns, contribution to pollution due to coal mining, rejecting the injection of CO₂ underground, adverse effects on geology, environmental community safety, potential dangers of CCS, diffuse impacts, effects on health, CO₂ as waste, leak exposition, earthquake risks near storage site and uncontrollable risks.

General conclusion: The main environmental concern of CCUS, and a factor hindering its social acceptability, is leakage. Other possible environmental impacts caused by CCUS have not received a comparable degree of attention.

- **TRUST**

	Trust
(-)	2
(+)	0
Conclusion (item)	Trust in government/industry
Level of evidence	VL
Level of agreement	

Level of evidence/level of agreement: VL=very low; L=Low; M=medium; H=High; VH=Very high. Other items with <2 articles: unfair process, trust in CO₂ is NO

General conclusion: Trust in different stakeholders involved in CCUS deployment as a barrier to this deployment does not seem to have received much attention in the literature and does not seem to have played a key role as a barrier.

- **INFORMATION PROVISION**

	Information provision
(-)	7
(+)	1
Conclusion (item)	Providing more information reduces the acceptability of CCUS
Level of evidence	M
Level of agreement	VH

Level of evidence/level of agreement: VL=very low; L=Low; M=medium; H=High; VH=Very high. Other items with <2 articles: Information framing or semantics

General conclusion: Providing more information reduces the acceptability of CCUS

- **ECONOMIC IMPACTS**

In this broad category, the four items (increased price, economic consequences, local economic benefits (those believing that CCUS will benefit the community economically are less likely to have a NIMBY reaction) and fall in local property value) had only one article per item. The results show that each item has a positive effect on acceptance. Therefore, the **general conclusion of the category** is that not much analysis on the economic impacts of CCUS as a barrier to the acceptability of its deployment has been carried out. The existing studies identify a few potential barriers in this regard.

4.3.3.2 Summary of barriers

The main findings on the impact of barriers on CCUS acceptability can be summarized as follows regarding the broad categories of drivers:

- Sociodemographic features of the respondents have a limited and sometimes ambiguous relation with CCUS acceptance, except in the case of gender (with women generally more opposed).
- Proximity to the CCS project has a clearly negative impact on CCS acceptance. Other aspects of the place of residence of respondents seem to play a limited role in this regard.
- The results show that, clearly, perception of the risks of CCUS negatively affects its acceptance
- The opinions on whether a higher awareness of the climate change challenge entails a greater CCUS support are mixed. Other aspects of ideology and worldviews have not played an important role in the literature.
- The greater the level of previous knowledge of CCUS, the lower the acceptability of CCUS.
- Respondents are highly critical with the role that CCUS can play in mitigation. There seems to be a concern that CCUS will deter investments in other mitigation technologies and, thus, deter mitigation.
- The acceptability of CCUS seems to be negatively related to the costs of CCUS and to its lower maturity compared to other mitigation technologies.
- The main environmental concern of CCUS, and a factor hindering its social acceptability, is leakage. Other possible environmental impacts caused by CCUS have not received a comparable degree of attention.
- Trust in different stakeholders involved in CCUS deployment as a barrier to this deployment does not seem to have received much attention in the literature and does not seem to have played a key role as a barrier.

- Providing more information reduces the acceptability of CCUS.
- Not much analysis on the economic impacts of CCUS as a barrier to the acceptability of its deployment has been carried out. The existing studies identify a few potential barriers in this regard
- The source of CO₂ may have an important role to play in the acceptability of CCUS. If the source of CO₂ is a coal-fired power plant, the setting is perceived less positively than if it includes biomass or industry). However, this is underresearched field of study.

4.3.4 Not relevant items.

Finally, an analysis of non-relevant items was undertaken (table 7). We just counted the number of articles in which a specific item is relevant or not relevant in the studies reviewed. If it is relevant it can either have a positive or a negative impact on acceptability. Relevance is taken in a broad meaning, i.e. not necessarily statistically significant. This is only the case for regression analysis and other inferential methods. But we also include studies which use descriptive statistics to identify if a specific item is important for CCUS acceptability (i.e., in case neutral opinions are dominant among respondents).

Table 7. Identification of non-relevant items						
Broad category	Item	Not relevant (1)	Relevant (2)	Total (3)	% RELEVANT (4)	RELEVANT? (5)
Sociodemographics	Age	14	8	22	36	NO
	Education	15	8	23	35	NO
	Income	8	6	14	43	NO
	Gender	13	17	30	57	?
Perceived risks and benefits	Perceived risks	5	40	45	89	YES
Proximity	Proximity, place of residence	2	13	15	87	YES
Ideology, worldview, climate change awareness, environmental awareness	Political Ideology	4	3	7	43	?
	Concern on CC	3	17	20	85	YES
Knowledge of CCUS	CCUS knowledge	10	13	23	57	?
Contribution to mitigation.	Effectiveness of CCUS for CC mitigation	3	22	25	88	YES
Perception of technoeconomic features of CCUS: costs, maturity	CCUS costs	1	5	6	83	YES
Environmental and security of supply benefits	env benefits	0	13	13	100	YES
	reduces FF dependence	0	4	4	100	YES
	leakage	0	9	9	100	YES
Trust	Trust in institutions (gov't)	7	1	8	13	NO
	(general)	4	1	5	20	NO
Information provision	Information provision	2	19	21	90	YES

Source: Own elaboration. Notes: (1) = Number of studies in which the specific item appears as not relevant; (2) = Number of studies in which the specific item appears as relevant; (3) = Total number of studies on the relevance/non-relevance of the item; (4) = Percentage of items with a relevant outcome; (5) = Overall assessment of the significance of the item in the studies reviewed (YES=the item is mostly relevant; NO= The item is mostly not relevant).

The results show that age, education, income and trust are not relevant, gender, political ideology and CCUS knowledge show mixed evidence in relevance and the remaining items are clearly relevant.

4.3.5 Synthesis.

A synthesis of the review regarding the influence of different factors is provided in the next table per broad category. We are particularly interested in those categories for which four conditions are fulfilled: 1) The net effect is clearly positive or negative; 2) There is a high relevance; 3) There is a high evidence; 4) There is a high agreement.

As it can be observed, benefit perception is a driver which meets the three conditions, and the same can be stated about leakage as a barrier. Proximity and risk perception have a strong net effect as a barrier but one is not relevant (risk perception) and in the other the level of evidence is intermediate (proximity).

Table 8. Synthesis of findings regarding the influence of different factors on CCUS acceptability (broad categories).					
Category (BROAD)	DRIVER	BARRIER	NET	RELEVANCE	EVIDENCE
Sociodemographic	+/0	-/0	0	NR	H
Proximity	0	--	--	R	M
Benefit perception	++		++	R	H
Risk perception		--	--	NR	H
CC awareness	++	?	+	NR	M
Pol. Ideology	0	0	0	NR	L
CCUS knowledge	+	-	?	NR	M
CC mitigation	++	-	+	NR	H
Technoec features	+	-	?	R	VL
Env impacts	+	-	?	R	L
Leakage		--	--	R	H
Trust	+/0	0	0	R	M
Information provision	+	-	?	R	M/H
Economic impacts	0	0	0	R	VL

Note: (+) means positive effect (driver) and (-) means negative effects (barrier). "NET" is the overall assessment of whether the category is a driver (+) or a barrier (-), "NR" and "R" means "not relevant" and "relevant", respectively. "H", "M", "L" and "VL" means high, medium, low and very low evidence, respectively.

5 CONCLUSIONS

Social acceptability is arguably one of the main barriers to the development and deployment of carbon capture, utilisation and storage (CCUS) technologies. Accordingly, subtask 6.2.1. of the CaLby2030 project is devoted to this topic. The aim of this deliverable is to meet the requirement of Subtask 6.2.1 of the Grant Agreement of the CaLby2030 project (page 35 of Part B), according to which a “systematic literature review” on the topic will be performed, looking for previous empirical analyses on the social acceptability of CCUS technologies. This methodology, widely accepted for social science investigations, will provide relevant insights on the drivers and barriers to the social acceptability of CCUS projects. D6.3 will report the results of this systematic literature review, which will feed into the design of the survey in subtask 6.2.2.

This deliverable has provided details on the procedure and the results of the systematic literature review, which has been restricted to English peer-reviewed articles which have used surveys as the main data collection method. 71 articles in the literature were considered to meet the requirements of the systematic review protocol defined by the research team. Major findings have been structured in three main themes, regarding the level of knowledge and awareness of CCUS, the level of the social acceptability of CCUS and the factors which represent drivers and barriers to such acceptability.

Although the comparability of the results from different studies is limited by the different theoretical approaches and methodologies used, some stylized facts on the awareness/knowledge of CCUS can be identified: 1) General knowledge levels for CCUS are low; 2) Compared to other energy technologies, CCUS is the least well-known. 3) Strong cross-country differences on the level of CCUS knowledge exist; 4) There are strong differences between general, national and local studies, with local knowledge being usually greater than awareness at the national level; 5) Differences between stages can be observed, with “storage” being the better known and “utilisation” being the least well-known. Two relevant knowledge gaps exist on the analysis of CCUS knowledge. One refers to the drivers, the other refers to the trends of CCUS awareness over time were

As with CCUS knowledge, comparability of the results of different studies on CCUS acceptability is difficult, because there are different ways to ask the question about it. However, the following conclusions can be inferred from the studies: 1) The acceptability of CCUS is neutral to slightly positive; 2) Considerable differences across countries exist; 3) There is strong evidence of NIMBY and NUMBY; 4) CCUS is generally less preferred than other climate mitigation options; 4) There are significant differences across CCUS alternatives, e.g., between CCU vs. CCS, different options for CCU, on-shore vs. off-shore storage, source of CO₂ (coal-fired power vs. biomass or industry), type of CO₂ removal (BECCs vs. DAC) and foreign sourced vs. domestically sourced CO₂. A main knowledge gap is that analyses of the time trend of acceptability of CCUS have been virtually missing.

Finally, the reviewed articles provide interesting insights on the analysis of the drivers and barriers to the acceptability of CCUS. An inductive approach was followed to extract the specific factors enhancing or inhibiting the acceptability of CCUS. These very specific factors were then grouped, leading to 9 broad categories. Then, an analysis of the direction of the impact of specific factor, the level of evidence on the specific factor as well as the level of agreement between different articles on the direction of the specific factor was carried out.

The main findings on the impact of drivers on CCUS acceptability can be summarized as follows:

- Socio-demographic variables have a limited explanatory power of CCUS acceptance
- Place of residence and proximity to the CCS or coal plant do not seem to have an impact on CCS acceptance.
- Benefit perception of CCUS plays a relevant role in explaining CCUS acceptance
- Awareness of the climate change problem leads to greater CCUS support. Other aspects related to ideology and worldviews have not been found to play an important role (underresearched).
- Previous knowledge of CCUS is clearly related in a positive manner with CCS support
- The contribution of CCUS to climate change mitigation is related to its acceptance.

- Several aspects of the perception of the technoeconomic features of CCUS are positively related to its acceptance, although this is clearly an underresearched area.
- The environmental benefits of CCUS are related to acceptance.
- Trust in different actors is positively related to CCUS acceptance, but to a limited extent
- The acceptability of CCUS is positively related to information provision.
- The economic impacts of CCUS do not have a relevant influence on its acceptability.
- Different applications and CCUS stages have different degree of acceptability.

The main findings on the impact of barriers on CCUS acceptability can be summarized as follows:

- Sociodemographic features of the respondents have a limited and sometimes ambiguous relation with CCUS acceptance, except in the case of gender (with women generally more opposed).
- Proximity to the CCUS project has a clearly negative impact on CCUS acceptance. Other aspects of the place of residence of respondents seem to play a limited role in this regard.
- The results show that, clearly, perception of the risks of CCUS negatively affects its acceptance
- The opinions on whether a higher awareness of the CC challenge entails a greater CCUS support are mixed. Other aspects of ideology and worldviews have not played an important role in the literature.
- The greater the level of previous knowledge of CCUS, the lower the acceptability of CCUS.
- Respondents are highly critical with the role that CCUS can play in mitigation. There seems to be a concern that CCS will deter investments in other mitigation technologies and, thus, deter mitigation.
- The acceptability of CCUS seems to be negatively related to the costs of CCUS and to its lower maturity compared to other mitigation technologies.
- The main environmental concern of CCUS, and a factor hindering its social acceptability, is leakage. Other possible environmental impacts caused by CCUS have not received a comparable degree of attention.
- Trust in different stakeholders involved in CCUS deployment as a barrier to this deployment does not seem to have received much attention in the literature and does not seem to have played a key role as a barrier.
- Providing more information reduces the acceptability of CCUS.
- Not much analysis on the economic impacts of CCUS as a barrier to the acceptability of its deployment has been carried out. The existing studies identify a few potential barriers in this regard
- The source of CO₂ may have an important role to play in the acceptability of CCUS. If the source of CO₂ is a coal-fired power plant, the setting is perceived less positively than if it includes biomass or industry). However, this is underresearched field of study.

A synthesis of the review regarding the influence of different factors is provided per broad category. We were particularly interested in those categories for which three conditions were fulfilled: 1) the net effects were clearly positive or negative; 2) there was a high relevance; 3) There was a high evidence. Benefit perception was a driver which met the three conditions, and the same could be stated about leakage as a barrier. Proximity and risk perception had a strong net effect as a barrier but one was not relevant (risk perception) and in the other the level of evidence was intermediate (proximity).

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Amikawa K., Hirabayashi S., Sato T. (2011). Public acceptance of subsea underground carbon storage. *Energy Procedia* 4, pages 6345-6352. DOI: 10.1016/j.egypro.2011.02.651
- Arning K., Offermann-van Heek J., Linzenich A, Kaetelhoen A, Sternberg A, Bardow A, Ziefle, M. (2019). Same or different? Insights on public perception and acceptance of carbon capture and storage or utilization in Germany. *Energy Policy* 15, pages 235-249. DOI: 10.1016/j.enpol.2018.10.039
- Arning K., Offermann-van Heek J., Sternberg A., Bardow A., Ziefle M. (2020). Risk-benefit perceptions and public acceptance of Carbon Capture and Utilization. *Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions* 35, pages 292-308. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eist.2019.05.003>
- Ashworth P., Sun Y., Ferguson M., Witt K., She S. (2019). Comparing how the public perceive CCS across Australia and China. *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control* 9, pages 125-133. DOI: 10.1016/j.ijggc.2019.04.008
- Booth A, Sutton A, Clowes M., Martyn-St James M. (2021). *Systematic Approaches to a Successful Literature Review*. 3rd ed. SAGE Publications.
- Boyd A., Hmielowska J., David P. (2017). Public perception of carbon capture and storage in Canada: Results of a national survey. *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control* 67, pages 1-9. DOI: 10.1016/j.ijggc.2017.10.010
- Braun, C. (2017). Not in My Backyard: CCS Sites and Public Perception of CCS. *Risk analysis* 12, pages 2264-2275. DOI: 10.1111/risa.12793
- Braun C., Merk C., Ponitzsch G., Rehdanz K., Schmidt, U. (2018). Public perception of climate engineering and carbon capture and storage in Germany: survey evidence. *Climate Policy* 14, pages 471-484. DOI: 10.1080/14693062.2017.1304888
- Broecks KPF., van Egmond S., van Rijnsoever FJ., Verlinde-van den Berg M., Hekkert MP. (2016). Persuasiveness, importance and novelty of arguments about Carbon Capture and Storage. *Environmental Science and Policy* 59, pages 58-66. DOI: 10.1016/j.envsci.2016.02.004
- Broecks K., Jack C., ter Mors E., Boomsma C., Shackley S. (2021). How do people perceive carbon capture and storage for industrial processes? Examining factors underlying public opinion in the Netherlands and the United Kingdom. *Energy Research and Social Science* 81, pages 1-10. DOI: 10.1016/j.erss.2021.102236
- Brunsting S., Mastop J., Kaiser M., Zimmer R., Shackley S., Mabon L., Howell R. (2015). CCS Acceptability: Social Site Characterization and Advancing Awareness at Prospective Storage Sites in Poland and Scotland. *Oil & Gas Science and Technology* 70(4), pages 767-784. DOI: 10.1016/j.egypro.2013.06.671
- Cohen MA., Tubb A. (2018). The impact of environmental regulation on firm and country competitiveness: A meta-analysis of the porter hypothesis. *Journal of the Association of Environmental and Resource Economists*, 5(2), 371-399. DOI: 10.2139/ssrn.2692919
- CQUniversity Library (2023). Framing your research question. CIMO. <https://libguides.library.cqu.edu.au/c.php?g=949210&p=6881304>
- Chen ZA. (2015). A large national survey of public perceptions of CCS technology in China. *Applied Energy* 158(15), pages 366-377.
- Cox E., Spence E., Pidgeon N. (2020). Public perceptions of carbon dioxide removal in the United States and the United Kingdom. *Nature Climate Change* 10, pages 744-749. DOI: 10.1016/j.apenergy.2015.08.046
- Chistov V., Aramburu N., & Carrillo-Hermosilla J. (2021). Open eco-innovation: A bibliometric review of emerging research. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 311. DOI: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.127627
- de Best-Waldhober M., Daamen D., Faaij A. (2009). Informed and uninformed public opinions on CO2 capture and storage technologies in the Netherlands. *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control* 3, pages 322-332. DOI: 10.1016/j.ijggc.2008.09.001
- de Best-Waldhober M., Daamen D., Ramirez A., Faaij A., Hendriks C., de Visser E. (2012). Informed public opinion in the Netherlands: Evaluation of CO2 capture and storage technologies in comparison with other CO2 mitigation options. *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control* 10, pages 169-180. DOI: 10.1016/j.ijggc.2012.05.023
- del Río P., Kiefer C.P. (2022). Which policy instruments promote innovation in renewable electricity technologies? A critical review of the literature with a focus on auctions. *Energy Research & Social Science* 89. DOI: 10.1016/j.erss.2022.102501
- del Río P., Kiefer C. (2023). Academic research on renewable electricity auctions: Taking stock and looking forward, *Energy Policy* 173, 113305 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2022.113305>
- Denyer D., Tranfield D. (2009). Producing a systematic review. In: *The Sage handbook of organizational research methods* (eds Buchanan, D.A. & Bryman, A.) pages 671-689. Sage Publications Ltd.
- Dowd AM., Itaoka K., Ashworth P., Saito A., de Best-Waldhober M. (2014). Investigating the link between knowledge and perception of CO2 and CCS: An international study. *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control* 28, pages 79-87. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijggc.2014.06.009>
- Duan H. (2010). The public perspective of carbon capture and storage for CO2 emission reductions in China. *Energy Policy* 38, pages 5281-5289. DOI: 10.1016/j.enpol.2010.05.040

- Dütschke E., Schumann D., Pietzner K., Wohlfarth K., Höller S. (2014). does it make a difference to the public where co2 comes from and where it is stored?. *Energy procedia* 63, pages 6999-7010. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2014.11.733>
- Dütschke E., Wohlfarth K., Höller S., Viebahn P., Schumann D., Pietzner K. (2016). Differences in the public perception of CCS in Germany depending on CO2 source, transport option and storage location. *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control* 53, pages 149-159. DOI: 10.1016/j.ijggc.2016.07.043.
- Ferguson M., Ashworth P. (2021). Message framing, environmental behaviour and support for carbon capture and storage in Australia. *Energy Research & Social Science* 53, pages 149-159. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2021.101931>
- Grashof K. (2019). Are auctions likely to deter community wind projects? And would this be problematic? *Energy Policy*, 125, 20-32. DOI: 10.1016/j.enpol.2018.10.010
- Grubb M., Drummond P., Poncia A., McDowall W., Popp D., Samadi S., . . . Pavan, G. (2021). Induced innovation in energy technologies and systems: a review of evidence and potential implications for CO2 mitigation. *Environmental Research Letters*, 16(4). DOI: 10.1088/1748-9326/abde07
- Haddaway NR, Pullin AS. (2014). The policy role of systematic reviews: past, present and future. *Springer Sci. Rev.* 2, 179–183. DOI: 10.1007/s40362-014-0023-1
- Ha-Duong M., Nadaï A., Campos AS. (2009). A survey on the public perception of CCS in France. *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control* 3, pages 633-640. DOI: 10.1016/j.ijggc.2009.05.003
- Huijts NMA., Midden CJH., Meijnders AL. (2007). Social acceptance of carbon dioxide storage. *Energy Policy* 35, pages 2780-2789. DOI: 10.1016/j.enpol.2006.12.007
- IRENA (2022). *World energy transitions Outlook 2022. 1.5° C pathway. Chapter 1, pages 30-41.* <https://www.irena.org/publications/2022/mar/world-energytransitions-outlook-2022>
- Itaoka, K., Saito A., Akai M (2005). Public acceptance of CO2 capture and storage technology: A survey of public opinion to explore influential factors. *Greenhouse Gas Control Technologies, Volume I* E.S. Rubin, D.W. Keith and C.F. Gilboy (Eds.). Elsevier, pages 1011-1019. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-008044704-9/50102-6>
- Itaoka K., Okuda Y, Saito A., Akai, M. (2009). Influential information and factors for social acceptance of CCS: the 2nd round survey of public opinion in Japan. *Greenhouse Gas Control Technologies* 1(1), pages 4803-4810. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2009.02.307>
- Itaoka, K., Aya Saito, A., Akai, M. (2011). A study on roles of public survey and focus groups to assess public opinions for CCS implementation. *Energy Procedia* 4 (2011) 6330–6337 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2011.02.649>
- Jones CR, Olfe-Kräutlein B, Naims H and Armstrong K (2017). The Social Acceptance of Carbon Dioxide Utilisation: A Review and Research Agenda. *Front. Energy Res.* 5(11), pages 1-12. DOI: 10.3389/fenrg.2017.00011
- Kaiser M., Zimmer R., Brunsting S., Mastop J., Pol M. (2014). Development of CCS projects in Poland. How to communicate with the local public?. *Energy Procedia* 51, pages 267-273. DOI: 10.1016/j.egypro.2014.07.031
- Karimi F., Toikka A. (2018). General public reactions to carbon capture and storage: Does culture matter?. *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control* 70, pages 193-201. DOI: 10.1016/j.ijggc.2018.01.012
- Karimi F., Toikka A., Hukkinen JI. (2016). Comparative socio-cultural analysis of risk perception of Carbon Capture and Storage in the European Union. *Energy Research and Social Science* 21, pages 114-122. DOI: 10.1016/j.erss.2016.06.024
- Koukouzas N. et al (2022). Current CO2 Capture and Storage Trends in Europe in a View of Social Knowledge and Acceptance. A Short Review. *Energies* 15, 5716. DOI: 10.3390/en15155716
- Kraeusel, J; Möst, D. (2012). Carbon Capture and Storage on its way to large-scale deployment: Social acceptance and willingness to pay in Germany. *Energy Policy* 49, pages 642-651. DOI: 10.1016/j.enpol.2012.07.006
- Krause RM., Carley SR., Warren DC., Rupp JA., Graham JD. (2014). Not in (or Under) My Backyard: Geographic Proximity and Public Acceptance of Carbon Capture and Storage Facilities. *Risk Analysis* 34(3), pages 529-540. DOI: 10.1111/risa.12119
- Kumar Kar S., Harichandan S. (2022). Green marketing innovation and sustainable consumption: A bibliometric analysis. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 361. DOI: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.132290.
- IPCC (2022). *Climate Change 2022. Mitigation of Climate Change. Working Group III contribution to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change.* https://report.ipcc.ch/ar6/wg3/IPCC_AR6_WGIII_Full_Report.pdf
- Li Q., Liu L.-C., Chen Z.-A., Zhang X., Jia L., Liu G. (2014). A survey of public perception of CCUS in China. *Energy Procedia* 63, pages 7019-7023. DOI: 10.1016/j.egypro.2014.11.735
- Linzenich A., Arning K., Offermann-van Heek J., Ziefle M. (2019). Uncovering attitudes towards carbon capture storage and utilization technologies in Germany: Insights into affective-cognitive evaluations of benefits and risks. *Energy Research and Social Science* 48, pages 205-218. DOI: 10.1016/j.erss.2018.09.017

- Linzenich A., Arning K., Ziefle M. (2021). Acceptance of energy technologies in context: Comparing laypeople's risk perceptions across eight infrastructure technologies in Germany. *Energy Policy* 152, 112071 pages 1-12. DOI: 10.1016/j.enpol.2020.112071.
- L'Orange S., Wallquist L., Dohle S., Siegrist M. (2011). Communication of CCS monitoring activities may not have a reassuring effect on the public. *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control* 5, pages 1674-1679. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijggc.2011.05.040>
- L'Orange S., Dohle S., Siegrist M. (2014). Public perception of carbon capture and storage (CCS): A review. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Review* 38, pages 848-863. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2014.07.017>
- Merk, C; Nordo, AD; Andersen, G; Laegreid, OM; Tvinneim, E. (2022). Don't send us your waste gases: Public attitudes toward international carbon dioxide transportation and storage in Europe. *Energy Research and Social Science* 1, 032071 pages 1-6. DOI: 10.1016/j.erss.2021.102450
- Midden C, Huijts N. (2009). The role of trust in the affective evaluation of novel risks: The case of CO₂ storage. *Risk Analysis* 9, pages 743-751. DOI: 10.1111/j.1539-6924.2009.01201.x
- Miller E., Bell L., Buys L. (2007). Public understanding of carbon sequestration in Australia: Socio-demographic predictors of knowledge, engagement and trust. *Australian journal of emerging technologies and society* 5(1), pages 15-33.
- Moon W., Kahlor LA, Olson H. (2020). Understanding public support for carbon capture and storage policy: The roles of social capital, stakeholder perceptions, and perceived risk/benefit of technology. *Energy Policy* 139, 111312, pages 1-10. DOI: 10.1016/j.enpol.2020.111312
- Moutenet JP., Bedard K., Malo M. (2012). Public awareness and opinion on CCS in the province of Quebec, Canada. *Greenhouse Gases-Science and Technology* 2, pages 126-135. DOI: 10.1002/ghg.1278
- Nielsen J., Stavrianakis K., Morrison Z. (2022). Community acceptance and social impacts of carbon capture, utilization and storage projects: A systematic meta-narrative literature review. *PLoS ONE*. 17(8): e0272409. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0272409>
- Offermann-van Heek J., Arning K., Linzenich A., Ziefle M. (2018). Trust and distrust in Carbon Capture and Utilization industry as relevant factors for the acceptance of carbon-based products. *Frontiers in Energy Research* 6. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenrg.2018.00073>
- Offermann-van Heek J.O., Arning K., Sternberg A., Bardow A., Ziefle, M. (2020). Assessing public acceptance of the life cycle of CO₂ -based fuels: Does information make the difference?. *Energy Policy* 143. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2020.111586>
- Oltra C., Sala R., Boso A. (2012). The influence of information on individuals' reactions to CCS technologies: results from experimental online survey research. *Greenhouse Gases-Science and Technology* 2, pages 209-215. DOI: 10.1002/ghg.1285
- Lima P., Pereira A., Chaves G., Meneguelo A. (2021). Environmental awareness and public perception on carbon capture and storage (CCS) in Brazil. *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control* 111, 103467, pages 1-11. DOI: 10.1016/j.ijggc.2021.103467
- Peñasco C., Anadón L.D., Verdolini E. (2021). Systematic review of the outcomes and trade-offs of ten types of decarbonization policy instruments. *Nature Climate Change*, 11(3), 257-265. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-020-00971-x>
- Perdan S., Jones C., Azapagic A. (2017). Public awareness and acceptance of carbon capture and utilisation in the U.K.. *Sustainable Production and Consumption* 10, pages 74-84. DOI: 10.1016/j.spc.2017.01.001
- Pianta S., Rinscheid A., Weber E. (2021). Carbon capture and storage in the United States: perceptions, preferences and lessons for policy. *Energy Policy* 151, 112149, pages 1-8. DOI: 10.1016/j.enpol.2021.112149
- Pietzner K, Schumann D, Tvedt SD, Torvatn HY, Naess R, Reiner DM, Anghel S, Cismaru D, Constantin C, Daamen DDL, Dudu A, Esken A, Gemeni V, Ivan L, Koukouzas N, Kristiansen G, Markos A, ter Mors E, Nihfidov OC, Papadimitriou J, Samoila IR, Sava CS, Stephenson MH, Terwel BW, Tomescu CE, Ziogou F. (2011). Public awareness and perceptions of carbon dioxide capture and storage (CCS): Insights from surveys administered to representative samples in six European countries. *Energy Procedia* 4, pages 6300-6306. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2011.02.645>
- Plamgren C., Morgan MG., Bruine W., Keith D. (2004). Initial public perceptions of deep geological and oceanic disposal of carbon dioxide. *Environmental Science and technology* 38(24), pages 6441-6450. DOI: 10.1021/es040400c
- Pullin A., Frampton G.K., Livoreli B., Petrokofsky G. (2018). Guidelines for Authors Environmental Evidence Retrieved from www.environmentalevidence.org/information-for-authors.
- Saito A., Itaoka K., Akai M. (2019). Those who care about CCS. Results from a Japanese survey on public understanding of CCS. *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control* 84, pages 121-130. DOI: 10.1016/j.ijggc.2019.02.014
- Schumann D. (2017). Public Perception of CO₂ Pipelines. *Energy Procedia* 114, pages 7356-7366. DOI: 10.1016/j.egypro.2014.11.744
- Schumann D., Dütschke E., Pietzner K. (2014). Public Perception of CO₂ Offshore Storage in Germany. Regional Differences and Determinants. *Energy Procedia* 63, pages 7096-7112. DOI: 10.1016/j.egypro.2014.11.744..
- Seigo SL, Arvai J., Dohle S., Siegrist M. (2014). Predictors of risk and benefit perception of carbon capture and storage (CCS) in regions with different stages of deployment. *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control* 25, pages 23-32. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijggc.2014.03.007>

- Shackley S., McLachlan C., Gough C. (2005). The public perceptions of carbon capture and storage in the UK: results from focus groups and a survey.. *Climate Policy* 4(4), pages 377-398. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14693062.2004.9685532>
- Shah, P; Wang, W; Yang, JZ; Kahlor, L; Anderson, J. (2022). Framing climate change mitigation technology: The impact of risk versus benefit messaging on support for carbon capture and storage. *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control* 119, 103737 pages 1-10. DOI: 10.1016/j.ijggc.2022.103737
- Shah P., Yang JZ., Kahlor L. (2023). Psychological distance, risk perception, and affect: Texas residents' support for carbon capture and storage. *Journal of Risk Research* 26(2), pages 184-198. DOI: 10.1080/13669877.2022.2116084
- Sharp J.D., Jaccard M.K., Keith D.W. (2009). Anticipating public attitudes toward underground CO₂ storage. *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control* 3, pages 641-651. DOI: 10.1016/j.ijggc.2009.04.001
- Sovacool B.K., Axsen J., Sorrell S. (2018). Promoting novelty, rigor, and style in energy social science: Towards codes of practice for appropriate methods and research design. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 45, 12-42. DOI:10.1016/j.erss.2018.07.007
- Steeper T. (2013). CO₂CRC Otway Project social research: assessing CCS community consultation. *Energy Procedia* 37, pages 7454-7461. DOI: 10.1016/j.egypro.2013.06.688
- Sun Y., Li Y., Cai BF., Li Q. (2020). Comparing the explicit and implicit attitudes of energy stakeholders and the public towards carbon capture and storage. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 254, 120051, pages 1-8. DOI: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.120051
- Tcvetkov P., Cherepovitsyn A., Fedoseev A. 2019. Public perception of carbon capture and storage: A state-of-the-art overview. *Heliyon* 5, e02845, pages 1-28. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2019.e02845>
- Terwel B., Daamen D. (2012). Initial public reactions to CCS: differentiating general and local views. *Climate Policy* 12(3), pages 288-300. DOI: 10.1080/14693062.2011.637819
- Terwel B., ter Mors E., Daamen D. (2012). It's not only about safety: Beliefs and attitudes of 811 local residents regarding a CCS project in Barendrecht. *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control* 9, pages 41-51. DOI: 10.1016/j.ijggc.2012.02.017
- Tokushige K., Akimoto K., Tomoda T. (2007a). Public perceptions on the acceptance of geological storage of carbon dioxide and information influencing the acceptance.. *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control* 1, pages 101-112. DOI: 10.1016/S1750-5836(07)00020-5
- Tokushige K., Akimoto K., Tomoda T. (2007b). Public acceptance and risk-benefit perception of CO₂ geological storage for global warming mitigation in Japan. *Mitigation and Adaption Strategies for Global Change* 12, pages 1237-1251. DOI: 10.1007/s11027-006-9037-6
- Toma L., Barnes A., Revoredo-Giha C., Tsononi V., Glenk K. (2014). A behavioural economics analysis of the impact of information and knowledge on CO₂ capture and storage acceptance in the European Union. *Procedia Economics and Finance* 14, pages 605-614. DOI: 10.1016/S2212-5671(14)00749-7
- Wallquist L., Visschers VHM., Siegrist M. (2010). Impact of knowledge and misconceptions on benefit and risk perception of CCS. *Environmental Science & Technology* 44, pages 6557-6562. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es1005412>
- Wallquist L., L'Orange Seigo S., Vivianne H.M., Visschers V., Siegrist M. (2012). Public acceptance of CCS system elements: A conjoint measurement. *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control* 6, pages 77-83. DOI: 10.1016/j.ijggc.2011.11.008
- Wang M., Wang S., Sun Y., Li Y. (2019). Improving Public Acceptance of Carbon Capture and Storage(CCS) in China. *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science* 371. DOI: 10.1088/1755-1315/371/3/032071
- Wang M., Gong YC., Wang S., Li Y., Sun Y. (2021). Promoting support for carbon capture and storage with social norms: Evidence from a randomized controlled trial in China. *Energy Research and Social Sciences* 74, 101979. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2021.10197>
- Warren D.C., Carley S.R., Krause R.M., Rupp J.A., Graham J.D. (2014). Predictors of attitudes toward carbon capture and storage using data on world views and CCSspecific attitudes. *Science and Public Policy* 41, pages 821-834. DOI: 10.1093/scipol/scu016
- Whitmarsh L., Xenias D., Jones C. (2019). Framing effects on public support for carbon capture and storage. *Palgrave communications* 5(17), pages 1-10. DOI: 10.1057/s41599-019-0217-x
- Witte K. (2021). Social acceptance of carbon capture and storage (CCs) from industrial applications. *Sustainability* 13, 12278, pages 1-29 <https://doi.org/10.3390/su132112278>
- Wolske K., Raimi K., Campbell-Arvai V., Hart P.S. (2019). Public support for carbon dioxide removal strategies: the role of tampering with nature perceptions. *Climate Change* 152, pages 345-361. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-019-02375-z>
- Yang L., Zhang X., McAlinden K. (2016). The effect of trust on people's acceptance of CCS technologies: Evidence from a survey in the People's Republic of China. *Energy* 96, pages 69-79. DOI: 10.1016/j.energy.2015.12.044

Carbon Science and Technology Institute

General information > infocalby2030@incar.csic.es

Project's manager > Javier Camús > j.camus@csic.es

Project's Coordinator > Carlos Abanades > abanades@incar.csic.es

www.calby2030.eu

Funded by
the European Union